

NEWA FORESTED HILL EXPERIMENT KASSEL

EXPERIMENT DOCUMENTATION

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Abstract

The NEWA Forested Hill Experiment Kassel was a field campaign conducted within the EU project – New European Wind Atlas NEWA. The experiment provides a unique dataset of wind measurements for validating models for flow over forested hilly terrain. It was performed around the »Rödeser Berg«, a hill located 20 km northwest of Fraunhofer IEE Kassel, Germany. The experiment consisted of a 3 month intensive campaign and a 1 year long-term campaign (November 2016 to October 2017). In total 17 wind measurement systems were used: 9 long-range Doppler scanning lidars, 6 lidar/sodar vertical wind profilers and 2 tall met masts.

By the end of the NEWA project all experimental data will be freely available. The measurement data will be provided in NetCDF format.

This technical report provides a detailed documentation of the field campaign.

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1 Preface

The Forested Hill Experiment Kassel was conducted within the EU project NEWA – New European Wind Atlas. The European Commission partly funded NEWA through FP7 (ERA-NET Plus, topic FP7-ENERGY.2013.10.1.2). National agencies provided additional funding: Danish Energy Agency, Department of Energy and Sustainable Building (Belgium, Wallonia), the government agency for Innovation by Science and Technology (Belgium, Flanders), Latvian Academy of Sciences, Swedish Energy Agency, Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (Portugal), the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey and Ministerio de Economía y Competitividad (Spain). Furthermore the German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy supported the NEWA project (grant No. 0325832A).

New European Wind Atlas

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2 Introduction

2.1 NEWA – New European Wind Atlas project

The New European Wind Atlas (NEWA) is a project concerned with

- i. creation of a freely accessible wind atlas covering the European Union, Turkey and European coastal water within 100 km off the shore;
- ii. development of models or a model chain to produce the high-resolution wind atlas;
- iii. atmospheric flow experiments in various kinds of complex terrain to validate the models.

The largest part of NEWA, and possibly also the longest lasting contribution to our knowledge about atmospheric flow for wind energy purposes, is a series of complex-terrain experiments. Common to all the experiments is the use of Doppler lidar systems to supplement and in some cases completely replace meteorological masts. A detailed overview of the complex terrain experiments in the New European Wind Atlas is given in Mann et al. 2017.

2.2 Kassel – a forested hill experiment

Centred around the existing 200 m mast of Fraunhofer IEE at Rödeser Berg near Kassel an experiment on patchy forest over hilly terrain was conducted in 2016 and 2017. The NEWA forested hill experiment in Kassel aims at characterizing the flow over Rödeser Berg in relevant heights of modern wind turbines. It provides a unique dataset for model validation in this terrain. The experiment consisted of an intensive and a long-term measurement campaign.

The main focus of the intensive three month campaign was the development of the flow over the ridge of the forested hill in the prevailing wind direction (about 217°). For this purpose, the flow along the main wind direction was probed with a dense array of instrumentation. Nine long-range Doppler scanning lidars (WindScanners) were deployed at the experiment. In conjunction with two tall meteorological masts and with four Doppler lidar- and two sodar wind profilers they mapped the flow »in a terrain type where underestimation of wind resources is not uncommon« (J. Mann et al. 2017, p. 3).

The one year long-term campaign with two tall masts started in parallel to the intensive campaign. Both meteorological masts with heights of 200 m and 140 m were equipped with sonic and cup anemometers at multiple levels.

In total 17 measurement systems were used in the NEWA Forested Hill Experiment Kassel: 9 scanning lidars, 6 lidar/sodar wind profilers and 2 tall met masts.

The following sections provide information about the measurement site Rödeser Berg (chapter 3), the measurement concept (chapter 4) and the setup of the measurement systems (met masts: chapter 5; wind profilers: chapter 6; scanning lidars: chapter 7).

3 General site description

The following chapter briefly describes the measurement site of the NEWA forested hill experiment Kassel. It includes figures of the terrain orography (contour lines and a shaded relief, chapter 3.1) as well as figures of land cover based on satellite imagery and CORINE land cover data (chapter 3.2) of an area of approximately 10x10 km², covering all measurement sites. A more detailed site characterisation can also be found in Pauscher et al. 2017, Pauscher et al. 2016 and Klaas et al. 2015.

Furthermore the chapter introduces more detailed forest data (forest height, forest density) that was prepared within the NEWA project (chapter 3.3).

The NEWA forested hill experiment Kassel was conducted around the existing 200 m tall met mast of Fraunhofer IEE at »Rödeser Berg«. The Rödeser Berg is a hill which is part of a ridge of hills in central Germany, see Fig. 01. The highest elevation is 417 m and located south of the measurement mast.

»The mast is located at the southwestern edge of a clearing (approx. 280 m north to south and 200 m east to west) on the ridge of the forested hill which stretches from approximately SSE to NNW.

The closer surroundings of the mast are characterized by forest of varying heights and several clearings. The distance, up to which the forest stretches, strongly varies with direction. In the direction NNW the forest extends about 5.8 km, while in ENE the forest edge is already reached within approximately 400 m from the mast.

The orography of the hill also varies strongly with direction. In general, the terrain is hilly and undulated. Towards NNW a hilly ridge extends for about 5.8 km. The wider surroundings consist of a patchy landscape of mainly agricultural land use, forest and some settlements. The immediate surroundings of the forested hill are mainly characterised by open agricultural areas. In the east and the west these are bordered by forested hills. In general, the terrain surrounding Rödeser Berg is very heterogeneous« (from Pauscher et al. 2017, p. 2).

Fig. 01 Location of the experiment site at Rödeser Berg near Kassel, Germany (relief map from Wikipedia).

3.1 Orography

In the course of the national scan of Hesse, performed by the Hessische Verwaltung für Bodenmanagement und Geoinformation (HVBG), airborne laser scanning (ALS) data was collected. The area around the Rödeser Berg was scanned between 2010-03-08 and 2010-03-25. The lidar system used consisted of an ALTM Gemini with an Applanix GPS and IMU. It was mounted on a Cessna 206 aircraft. The mean scanning density is 5.4 pulses/m² and the average point density of the point cloud (all returns) is 9.1 points/m². The terrain elevation is calculated by the median height of the ground points within each 10 x 10 m² grid cell (Freier 2017).

The results are shown in Fig. 02 and Fig. 03 for the area of 10 x 10 km² around Rödeser Berg. The transect line of the intensive campaign (from southwest to northeast) at 217° and the measurement systems along the transect are also plotted in the figures, see chapter 4.1 for the experimental setup.

Fig. 02 Contour lines for the measurement area. Each contour line represents a 10 m elevation step. Colours indicate the terrain elevation reaching from 200 m (blue colours) to 600 m (red colours). White diamonds mark the 140 m and 200 m mast (MM140, MM200), the lidar profiler WP1 and the sodar profiler WP5 from southwest to northeast. Coordinates are UTM 32 N in meters. Source: Freier 2017, Data source: HVBG

Fig. 03 Shaded relief for the measurement area that illustrates the terrain ruggedness. Colours indicate the terrain elevation reaching from 200 m (blue colours) to 600 m (red colours). White diamonds mark the 140 m and 200 m mast (MM140, MM200), the lidar profiler WP1 and the sodar profiler WP5 from southwest to northeast. Coordinates are UTM 32 N in meters. Source: Freier 2017, Data source: HVBG

3.2 Land cover

Fig. 04 shows a satellite image taken from Google Earth for the measurement area around Rödeser Berg. The image covers an area of approx. 20 x 20 km² around the 200 m mast site.

The land cover (10 x 10 km²) is shown on the basis of CORINE land cover (CLC) data. CLC data is taken from the CLC10 data set based on LBM-DE2012 data set that contains land use and land cover data (Fig. 05). Both data sets are in vector format. The CLC10 data set is a generalized version of the LBM-DE2012 data set containing areas with a size of at least 10 ha. CLC10 data are available free of charge at the Service Centre of the Federal Government for Geo-Information and Geodesy www.geodatenzentrum.de (GeoBasis-DE 2012).

Fig. 04 Satellite image of measurement area. The 200 m tall met mast (MM200) at Rödeser Berg is located in the centre of the shown area. Source: Google Earth

Fig. 05 Land cover map of the measurement area on the basis of CORINE land cover (CLC) data. CLC data is taken from the CLC10 data set based on LBM-DE2012 data set that contains land use and land cover data. The map shows the different land use classes from which roughness parameterization might be derived. Coordinates are UTM 32 N in meters.

3.3 Forest

The forested areas surrounding the Roedeser Berg are heterogeneous in terms of tree species and age. To get a better data basis for flow simulation more detailed information about the forest was derived from the airborne lidar measurements described in chapter 3.1. From the lidar measurements the forest heights and forest densities were derived.

The maximum vegetation height is calculated by the height of the maximum vegetation return within each 10 x 10 m² grid cell subtracted by the elevation of the ground (Fig. 06).

The plant area index is derived from the sum of the plant area density within each canopy level. The vertical resolution for the calculation of the PAI is 1 m. The method used for the determination of the forest density is based on the Beer-Lambert law: $PAI = -\frac{1}{k} * \ln\left(\frac{I}{I_0}\right)$. k is the extinction coefficient, and I/I_0 is the transmittance of the canopy which is defined as the ratio of the number of first echoes from the canopy to the total number of first echoes within each bin (Fig. 07). A detailed description can be found in Freier (2017). The derived data is freely available on the NEWA data server.

Fig. 06 Map of forest heights in the measurement area. White diamonds mark the 140 m and 200 m mast (MM140, MM200), the lidar profiler WP1 and the sodar profiler WP5 from southwest to northeast. Coordinates are UTM 32 N in meters. Data is derived by Freier 2017 from the airborne lidar measurements described in chapter 3.1.

Fig. 07 Map of forest density (PAI) in the measurement area. White diamonds mark the 140 m and 200 m mast (MM140, MM200), the lidar profiler WP1 and the sodar profiler WP5 from southwest to northeast. Coordinates are UTM 32 N in meters. Data is derived by Freier 2017 from the airborne lidar measurements described in chapter 3.1.

3.4 Nearby wind farms

At the beginning of the experiment there were two wind farms in the measurement area: One wind farm is located west of the Rödeser Berg (Ehringen), consisting of five Vestas V47 turbines. The other wind farm is located on top of the Rödeser Berg consisting of four Enercon E-101 turbines. A third wind farm (Escheberg) was installed northeast of the Rödeser Berg during the year 2017. It consists of four Nordex N117 turbines.

Tab. 01 to Tab. 04 give the coordinates and types of the turbines as well as information on hub heights, total heights and rotor diameters. In case of the newly installed wind farm (Escheberg) an additional table states relevant dates during the installation and commissioning phase. A Google Earth kmz-File is provided with the dataset that covers the measurement sites as well as the surrounding turbine sites on the NEWA data server. For a satellite image with the locations of wind farms see Fig. 08.

General site description

Turbine ID	Easting; Northing	Turbine type	Rotor diameter	Hub height	Total height
V47-WT1	511040; 5689538	Vestas V-47	47 m	65 m	88,5 m
V47-WT2	510768; 5689565	Vestas V-47	47 m	65 m	88,5 m
V47-WT3	510584; 5689894	Vestas V-47	47 m	65 m	88,5 m
V47-WT4	510812 5690094	Vestas V-47	47 m	65 m	88,5 m
V47-WT5	510512; 5690220	Vestas V-47	47 m	65 m	88,5 m

Tab. 01 Coordinates and specifications of wind turbines in the wind farm Ehringen. Coordinates are UTM 32 N in meters.

Turbine ID	Easting; Northing	Turbine type	Rotor diameter	Hub height	Total height
E101-WT1	513762; 5689921	Enercon E-101	101 m	135 m	186 m
E101-WT2	513440; 5690294	Enercon E-101	101 m	135 m	186 m
E101-WT3	513045; 5690650	Enercon E-101	101 m	135 m	186 m
E101-WT4	512760; 5690841	Enercon E-101	101 m	135 m	186 m

Tab. 02 Coordinates and specifications of wind turbines at Rödeser Berg. Coordinates are UTM 32 N in meters.

Turbine ID	Easting; Northing	Turbine type	Rotor diameter	Hub height	Total height
N117-WT1	516420; 5694632	Nordex N 117	116.3 m	140.6 m	199 m
N117-WT2	516134; 5694210	Nordex N 117	116.3 m	140.6 m	199 m
N117-WT3	516158; 5693710;	Nordex N 117	116.3 m	140.6 m	199 m
N117-WT4	515715; 5693934	Nordex N 117	116.3 m	140.6 m	199 m

Tab. 03 Coordinates and specifications of wind turbines near WP5 (wind farm Escheberg). Coordinates are UTM 32 N in meters.

Tab. 04 Important dates during the construction phases of the wind turbines near WP5 (wind farm Escheberg)

Turbine ID	Completion of tower	Completion of rotor	Commissioning date
N117-WT1	24 April 2017	5 January 2017	31 May 2017
N117-WT2	5 January 2017	27 April 2017	18 May 2017
N117-WT3	6 March 2017	10 May 2017	23 May 2017
N117-WT4	27 March 2017	17 May 2017	31 May 2017

Fig. 08 Overview over the positions of two met mast and the wind turbines in relation to the measurement transect. The wind farm in the west consists of five Vestas V47-660 kW wind turbines and the wind farm at Rödeser Berg consists of four E101-3000 kW wind turbines. The wind farm northeast was erected in 2017 and consists of four Nordex N117 turbines.

Source: Google Earth

4 Measurement concept

The following chapter describes the overall measurement concept of the NEWA Forested Hill Experiment Kassel. Section 4.1 gives the main objectives and describes the experimental setup including the transect of the intensive campaign. Section 4.2 provides a detailed overview over all measurement sites and devices used throughout the experiment. A time table of the measurement period is given in section 4.4.

4.1 Experimental setup

Rödeser Berg – a typical wind farm site in central Germany - has been chosen as a reference case for the flow situation over a forested hill in a patchy landscape, see chapter 3. The measurement campaign is focussed on the flow above and around the Rödeser Berg. The hill is aligned orthogonal to the main wind direction (southwest and northeast).

The experiment consisted of a 3 month intensive campaign (from October 2016 to January 2017) and a 1 year long-term measurement campaign. The 1 year long-term campaign with two tall masts started in parallel to the intensive campaign. Both meteorological masts with heights of 200 m and 140 m were equipped with sonic and cup anemometers at multiple levels.

The main focus of the intensive measurement campaign was the development of the flow over the ridge of the forested hill in the prevailing wind direction. A 5.5 km long transect along the main wind direction at 217° has been chosen as the flow line of main interest. The transect is split into two parts: upwind and downwind of the hill. The transect was probed with a dense array of instrumentation. The inflow conditions were determined with a 140 m tall mast, which also marks the start of the transect. This mast was equipped with sonic and cup anemometers at 9 heights to allow for the characterization of wind and turbulence conditions. The 200 m tall met mast is equipped with sonic anemometers at 9 height levels and a dense array of cup anemometers measured the vertical wind profile at the top of Rödeser Berg. The end of the transect was marked by a lidar wind profiler.

Fig. 09 provides an overview over the measurement area and shows the location of the transect. A cross section through the terrain along the transect is given in Fig. 10. Fig. 11 to Fig. 14 show views along the transect taken from the start and from the end of the transect as well as from the top of Rödeser Berg.

Measurement concept

Fig. 09 Satellite image of the measurement area including the measurement sites MM140 (start of transect), MM200 (atop Rödeser Berg) and WP1 (end of transect) that are aligned along the measurement transect (green line). WP5 lies on the extension of the transect line about 3 km northeast of WP1. The circle indicates a radius of 6 km around MM200 which includes all measurement devices.

Source: Google Earth

Fig. 10 Terrain slice along the 217° transect from southwest to northeast (left to right). From left to right the red dots mark MM140, MM200 and WP1. Please note that due to the axis-scaling the terrain inclination is exaggerated.

Fig. 11 View along the southwest (upwind) part of the transect line from the start of the transect towards Rödeser Berg and the 200 m mast (MM200) - viewing direction: northeast. The picture was taken from the top of the 140 m mast (MM140).

Date: 7 Oct 2016

Photo courtesy Ge:Net

Fig. 12 View along the southwest (upwind) part of the transect line towards the measurement site of the 140 m mast (MM200) - viewing direction: southwest. The picture was taken from the top of the 200 m mast (MM200).

Date: 15 Jul 2015.

Photo courtesy of TELECONTRACTING SCANDINAVIA AB

Fig. 13 View along the northeast (downwind) part of the transect line towards the measurement site of the lidar profiler (WP1) that marks the end of the transect - viewing direction: northeast. The picture was taken from the top of the 200 m mast (MM200).
Date: 15 Jul 2015.
Photo courtesy of TELECONTRACTING SCANDINAVIA AB

Fig. 14 View along the northeast (downwind) part of the transect line towards Rödeser Berg and the 200 m mast (MM200) - viewing direction: southwest. The picture was taken from the measurement site of the lidar profiler (WP1) that marks the end of the transect.
Date: 8 Sep 2016

In combination with the two tall masts, remote sensing devices and, in particular, multi-lidar measurements formed the backbone of the experiment. Two sets of synchronized long-range Doppler scanning wind lidars were used to create several virtual masts along a transect in step stare scanning mode. The location of the 140 m mast marked the starting point of the transect. The vertical wind profile of the 140 m mast was extended using a long-range lidar profiler (Windcube WLS 70) to heights of several hundred meters/few kilometres. This allows for the characterization of the flow aloft. The virtual masts were placed along the line between the 140 m mast crossing the 200 m tall mast and extending about 2 km behind the ridge of the hill. For each flow line (upwind and downwind of the hill), two synchronized WindScanners were used. The measurement heights of the virtual masts were set at 60 m (minimum realistic tip height above ground in forested areas) and at 135 m a. g. l. (hub height of the wind turbines on top of Rödeser Berg). Additional sampling points along the transect were provided by 2 wind profile lidars to support the virtual met masts and to provide continuous information on the wind conditions at the end of the flow line.

Using the plan position indicator (PPI) mode, additional WindScanners measured the flow in front of the hill. The PPI overlay provides insights into the spatial distribution of the flow over the hill. As the number of vertical wind profilers (4 lidars and 2 sodars) and virtual masts was limited, additional information on the wind profile along the main stream line (transect along main wind direction) was desirable. Therefore, additional WindScanners carried out a range height indicator (RHI) scan from the start of the transect (location of the 140 m mast) and two from the 200 m mast to the end of the flow line. 4 additional sites for wind profilers were selected in such a way that they could measure the incoming wind from other wind directions than the main wind direction.

All measurement devices were placed and configured in a suitable way to assess the flow along the transect as well as in front (southwest, upwind) and behind (northeast, downwind) the hill (inflow and outflow) and in the wider surroundings (also see Fig. 15, Fig. 16, Tab. 05 and Tab. 07).

From southwest to northeast the flow along the transect was measured by (IDs of the measurement devices in parentheses):

1. The 140 m tall met mast to measure the inflow conditions (MM140)
2. A lidar profiler for great heights next to the 140 m mast (WP6)
3. A standard lidar profiler in the slope of the hill (WP3)
4. The 200 m tall met mast on top of the hill (MM200)
5. A standard lidar profiler in the lee of the hill (WP1)
6. A standard sodar profiler on a subsequent hill (WP5)

Additionally the following measurement devices have been used to measure the flow surrounding the hill (IDs of the measurement devices in parentheses):

- 2 lidar scanners as synchronized multi-lidar systems to measure the flow along the transects at multiple points upwind the hill (WS4 and WS5)
- 2 lidar scanners as synchronized multi-lidar systems to measure the flow along the transects at multiple points downwind the hill (WS7 and WS8)
- 1 lidar scanner to perform RHI scans upwind the hill (WS1)
- 2 lidar scanners to perform RHI scans downwind the hill (WS2 and WS6)
- 2 lidar scanners to perform PPI scans upwind the hill (WS3 and WS9)
- 1 standard sodar profiler to measure the wind profile west of the hill (WP2)
- 1 standard lidar profiler to measure the wind profile south west of the hill (WP4)

In total 17 measurement systems were used: 9 scanning lidars, 6 lidar/sodar vertical wind profilers, 2 met masts. The 2 masts were measuring for one year in parallel (long-term measurements).

The following chapters 5, 6 and 7 give a more detailed description of the measurement devices and setup.

4.2 Measurement sites

The satellite images in Fig. 15 and Fig. 16 contain the locations and IDs of all measurement devices/systems. A Google Earth kmz-File is provided with the dataset that covers all measurement sites as well as all surrounding turbine sites and the measurement transect.

Fig. 15 Overview over the positions of the scanning lidars/WindScanners (WS) in relation to the measurement transect. Source: Google Earth

Fig. 16 Overview over the positions of the lidar (blue) and sodar (green) wind profilers (WP) in relation to the measurement transect. Source: Google Earth

Tab. 05 contains all measurement devices used within the intensive measurement campaign. The table gives the site name and a unique ID for each measurement device. Additionally, it gives the name or serial number, the type of measurement system, the manufacturer as well as the coordinates and elevation.

The coordinates in Tab. 05 are UTM 32 N coordinates that were measured during the installation of the measurement devices via GPS (lidar profilers, sodar profilers and masts) or differential GPS (WindScanners). For GPS measurements the elevation was extracted from the digital elevation model. For differential GPS elevation was also measured by differential GPS. The position measurement of the WindScanners was taken at the position of the WindScanner head with an accuracy of 1 cm to 2 cm.

Tab. 05 Measurement sites and devices. All measurement devices have a unique ID. Coordinates are UTM 32 N in meters. Elevation gives height with reference to WGS84 in meters.

Site	ID	Name or S/N	Type	Make	Easting; Northing	Elevation
MM140	MM140	MM140	Mast	Ge:Net	511589.36; 5687521.12	261.0
MM200	MM200	MM200	Mast	Telecon	513590.52; 5690182.54	388.0
WP1	WP1	#164	Lidar profiler	Leosphere Windcube v2	514804; 5691869	254.6
WP2	WP2	#358	Sodar profiler	Vaisala Triton	509942; 5690646	249.8
WP3	WP3	#72	Lidar profiler	Leosphere Windcube v1	512555; 5688544	273.1
WP4	WP4	#317	Lidar profiler	ZephIR 300	511524; 5684924	266.6
WP5	WP5	AJ03	Sodar profiler	AQSystems AQ500	516522; 5694134	341.0
MM140	WP6	Alize	Lidar profiler	Leosphere WLS-70	511642; 5687589	260.8
MM140	WS1	Vara	Lidar scanner	Leosphere WLS-200S	511641; 5687591	260.8
MM200	WS2	#23	Lidar scanner	Leosphere WLS-200S	513588.56; 5690177.75	392.8
MM140	WS3	#57	Lidar scanner	Leosphere WLS-200S	511640; 5687592	260.8
SSW	WS4	Sirocco	Lidar scanner	Leosphere WLS-200S	510686.85; 5687916.63	287.4
SW	WS5	#24	Lidar scanner	Leosphere WLS-200S	511044.39; 5689538.29	277.7
MM200	WS6	#58	Lidar scanner	Leosphere WLS-200S	513588.18; 5690176.48	392.8
North	WS7	#59	Lidar scanner	Leosphere WLS-200S	513640.85; 5692217.07	285.2
NE	WS8	Koshava	Lidar scanner	Leosphere WLS-200S	517029.65; 5690931.40	315.7
SW	WS9	#17	Lidar scanner	Leosphere WLS-200S	511043.50; 5689544.91	278.1

4.3 Overview of measurement variables collected at different measurement sites

Tab. 06 provides a quick overview of the measurement variables collected at the different measurement sites. Please note that the list is not comprehensive.

Site and equipment			Available data			
Site	ID	Type	Wind profile (horizontal speed and direction)	Turbulence data (wind and sonic temperature)	Radial wind speed	Standard met data (temperature, pressure, humidity)
MM140	MM140	Mast	x	x	n.a.	x
MM200	MM200	Mast	x	x	n.a.	x
WP1	WP1	Lidar profiler	x		x	
WP2	WP2	Sodar profiler	x			
WP3	WP3	Lidar profiler	x		x	
WP4	WP4	Lidar profiler	x		x	
WP5	WP5	Sodar profiler	x			
MM140	WP6	Lidar profiler	x		x	
MM140	WS1	Lidar scanner			x	
MM200	WS2	Lidar scanner			x	
MM140	WS3	Lidar scanner			x	
SSW	WS4	Lidar scanner			x	
SW	WS5	Lidar scanner			x	
MM200	WS6	Lidar scanner			x	
North	WS7	Lidar scanner			x	
NE	WS8	Lidar scanner			x	
SW	WS9	Lidar scanner			x	

Tab. 06 Overview of measured data by different stations during the experiment.

4.4 Measurement period

The installation and dismounting dates of all devices can be found in Tab. 07. The intensive measurement campaign started 12 October 2016 and ended early January 2017. The long term measurement campaign continued until End of October 2017.

Several of the WindScanners and Lidar profilers were already installed before the start of the intensive measurement campaign (relevant measurements). In the time before the start of the relevant, the measurement configuration was tested, WindScanners were levelled and aligned properly and the final measurement scenarios were programmed.

Tab. 07 Installation and dismounting dates of all measurement devices and measurement tasks.
RHI: Range Height Indicator
PPI: Plane Position Indicator
CT: Complex Trajectory (multi lidar to measure the flow along the transects at multiple points)

ID	Installation date	Start of relevant measurements	Dismounting date	Measurement task
MM140	12.10.2016	12.10.2016	31.10.2017	wind profile
MM200	Previously installed	12.10.2016	Still running	wind profile
WP1	02.09.2016	-	30.01.2017	wind profile
WP2	01.08.2016	-	07.03.2017	wind profile
WP3	27.10.2016	-	20.03.2017	wind profile
WP4	11.10.2016	-	04.01.2017	wind profile
WP5	03.08.2016	-	13.08.2017	wind profile
WP6	10.10.2016	-	04.01.2016	wind profile
WS1	24.10.2016	27.10.2016	03.01.2017	RHI
WS2	24.10.2016	27.10.2016	03.01.2017	RHI
WS3	13.10.2016	18.11.2016	17.01.2017	PPI
WS4	06.09.2016	17.10.2016	04.01.2017	CT (virtual masts)
WS5	16.08.2016	03.11.2016	03.01.2017	CT (virtual masts)
WS6	24.10.2016	19.11.2016	03.01.2017	RHI
WS7	08.08.2016	17.10.2016	03.01.2017	CT (virtual masts)
WS8	06.09.2016	17.10.2016	04.01.2017	CT (virtual masts)
WS9	01.12.2017	02.12.2016	03.01.2017	PPI

5 Measurement masts

Two tall masts provide the basis for the long-term campaign of the NEWA Forested Hill Experiment Kassel. Their purpose was to collect information about the vertical wind profiles in front, i. e. southwest, upwind of Rödeser Berg (ID 140 m tall mast: MM140) and at the top of the hill (ID 200 m tall mast: MM200) over a period of one year. This section details the measurement sites as well as the configuration of the two met masts.

5.1 200 m mast

Fraunhofer IEE erected a met mast with a nominal height of 200 m (MM200) at the top of Rödeser Berg in 2012. For the NEWA experiment two scanning lidars (WS2 and WS6) were located on the Rödeser Berg right next to the 200 m mast. The lidars were installed atop the intermodal container in which the data loggers for the mast are located.

The data availability of the mast measurements and of the remote sensing wind profilers (lidar and sodar) is shown in Fig. 17.

Fig. 17 Data availability of mast measurements and wind profilers at 135 m measurement height.

5.1.1 Site description

»The vicinity of the measurement site mainly consists of forested areas. The forest type at the Rödeser Berg is a mixed forest mainly consisting of beech trees, pine trees, spruces with a few areas of larches and oaks. There are several clearings, forest roads and some scattered houses close to the forest edges. The Rödeser Berg is very representative for typical mixed forests in Germany« (Freier 2017, p. 23).

The mast and the scanning lidars are placed in an area of the hill where Cyclone Kyrill denuded most of the trees in 2007. In the meantime the trees start growing back again. In 2014 a wind farm of four wind turbines was installed along the ridge of the hill. Fig. 08 shows an aerial view of Rödeser Berg and the locations of the four wind turbines. Tab. 02 provides details about the locations and specifications of the wind turbines. Fig. 18 provides a 360° panorama view of the measurement site from July 2017. Fig. 20 and Fig. 21 are taken from the neighbouring wind turbines. They depict the 200 m mast and its surrounding in winter and summer.

Fig. 18 360° panorama view of the measurement site of the 200 m tall mast and of the co-located scanning lidars WS2 and WS6 (date: July 2017).

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Measurement masts
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Fig. 19 Satellite image of the area surrounding the measurement location of MM200, WS2 and WS6;
Source: Google Earth

Fig. 20 200 m tall mast and surrounding in wintertime (date: February 2015). The Photograph was taken from wind turbine E101-WT2 (viewing direction: southeast). Photo courtesy of Stadtwerke Wolfhagen, Dieter Spangenberg

Fig. 21 200 m tall mast and surrounding in summer (date: June 2015). In the background: E101-WT2, -WT3 and -WT4. Photo taken from wind turbine E101-WT1 (viewing direction: northwest)
Photo courtesy of Stadtwerke Wolfhagen, Dieter Spangenberg

5.1.2

Mast design and instrumentation

The 200 m high mast is conforming to IEC 61400-12-1. It consists of a quadratic lattice structure with a side length of 1.05 m (Cue Dee K1050). The mast is composed of 98 segments, each with a height of 2 m. »The solidity of the mast structure is 0.220 for the lower section (below 160 m) and 0.204 for the upper section (above 160 m). Here, solidity is defined according to IEC 61400-12-1 as the projected area of all structural members divided by the exposed area of the mast« (Pauscher et al. 2017, p. 2). The top segment of the mast has a side length of 0.6 m (Cue Dee K600). Attached to it is a vertical tube on which the top anemometer is mounted.

The mast is oriented so that the booms can be clamped to the face of the mast and extended normal to the prevailing wind direction. Long booms with a length of 5.4 m are used as mounts for the wind sensors, i. e. cup anemometers, sonic anemometers and wind vanes. Shorter booms are used for other meteorological sensors, e. g. air pressure, temperature and relative humidity. The booms are oriented into two directions at about 140° and 320° to true north. The mast has a slight counter clockwise torsion of about 6° towards the top (e. g. southeast-booms at 20 m are oriented at 141° and 135° at 191 m; northwest-booms at 10 m are oriented at 322° and 315° at 191 m). The orientations of the booms are given in Tab. 08 and Tab. 09.

The mast is guyed to twelve foundations in four directions at 6°, 93°, 189° and 281° to true north around the mast base. The three foundations in each direction are approximately 40 m, 70 m and 100 m from the base of the mast. In total 44 guy wires are used at 10 heights (11 for each direction). Four aerial marker balls are used at the outer guy wires in each of the four directions.

Fig. 22 shows the view from the ground of the booms on the mast. Some radiation shields of temperature sensors at short booms are visible at the bottom of the picture. The climbing rail inside the lattice structure of the mast and in the upper part of the photo some aerial marker balls are also visible. Drawings with dimensions of the mast, the mast segments, guy wires and the booms as well as information on heights and orientations are given in the mast installation report (Telecon 2012). Telecontracting Scandinavia AB (Telecon) installed the mast in 2012.

The 200 m tall measurement mast is equipped with sonic anemometers at 9 height levels. Additionally a dense array of cup anemometry is installed at the mast, summing up to 15 height levels for wind measurements in total, see Fig. 23. Tab. 08 and Tab. 09 provide a complete list of wind sensors installed at the 200 m mast during the NEWA forested hill experiment. The data sheets of the sensors can be found in the Appendix.

Fig. 22 View from the ground to the 5.4 m long booms on the 200 m mast (MM200)

Windmeßmast Wolfhagen

Auftraggeber: Fraunhoferinstitut IWES - Kassel

- 0227** Anemometer THIES FC unbeheizt
- 0243** Anemometer WAA252 beheizt
- 0228** Anemometer THIES FC beheizt
- 0276** Sonic METEK uSonic 3
0266 Sonic GILL HS50
- 0256** Sonic THIES beheizt
- 0327** Windfahne THIES FC unbeheizt
- 0328** Windfahne THIES FC beheizt
- 0445** Temperatursensor
- 0535** Thermo-Hygrosensor
- 0461 A** Temperatursensor (oben)
- 0461** Temperaturdifferenzmeßumformer
- 0461 B** Temperatursensor (unten)
- 0618** Drucksensor
- 0892** Pyranometer +
0892 T Meßumformer
- 0822** Niederschlagssensor YOUNG beheizt
- 0837** Niederschlagswächter THIES beheizt
- 4101** WebCam MOBOTIX M12
- 2822** Hindernisfeuer LANTHAN HF102
- 0903-44-X** Schaltschrank
- 0103** Datenlogger
0103-X Datenlogger

Fig. 23 Instrumentation and mast layout of the 200 m tall met mast (MM200)

Tab. 08 Installed anemometers at the 200 m met mast (MM200) sorted by measurement height

Height	Sensor type	Sensor model	Sampling frequency	Orientation	Heated
10 m	Cup	Thies Clima First Class Advanced	1 Hz	322°	no
20 m	Cup	Thies Clima First Class Advanced	1 Hz	141°	no
20 m	Sonic	METEK uSonic-3 Scientific	40 Hz	322°	yes
30 m	Sonic	METEK uSonic-3 Scientific	40 Hz	322°	yes
40 m	Cup	Thies Clima First Class Advanced	1 Hz	141°	no
40 m	Sonic	Sonic Gill HS 50	50 Hz	322°	no
60 m	Cup	Vaisala WAA252	1 Hz	141°	yes
60 m	Sonic	METEK uSonic-3 Scientific	40 Hz	321°	yes
80 m	Cup	Thies Clima First Class Advanced	1 Hz	140°	heated bearing
80 m	Sonic	Thies Clima Ultrasonic Anemometer 3D	20 Hz	320°	yes
100 m	Cup	Thies Clima First Class Advanced	1 Hz	140°	no
100 m	Sonic	METEK uSonic-3 Scientific	40 Hz	320°	yes
120 m	Cup	Thies Clima First Class Advanced	1 Hz	139°	heated bearing
120 m	Cup	Thies Clima First Class Advanced	1 Hz	319°	heated bearing
135 m	Cup	Thies Clima First Class Advanced	1 Hz	137°	no
135 m	Sonic	Sonic Gill HS 50	50 Hz	318°	yes
140 m	Sonic	Thies Clima Ultrasonic Anemometer 3D	20 Hz	318°	yes
160 m	Cup	Thies Clima First Class Advanced	1 Hz	136°	no
160 m	Cup	Thies Clima First Class Advanced	1 Hz	317°	no
180 m	Cup	Vaisala WAA252	1 Hz	135°	yes
180 m	Cup	Thies Clima First Class Advanced	1 Hz	315°	heated bearing
188 m	Sonic	METEK uSonic-3 Scientific	40 Hz	315°	yes
191 m	Cup	Thies Clima First Class Advanced	1 Hz	135°	no
191 m	Cup	Thies Clima First Class anemometer	1 Hz	315°	no
200 m	Cup	Thies Clima First Class Advanced	1 Hz	top	heated bearing

Tab. 09 Installed wind vanes at the 200 m met mast (MM200) sorted by measurement height

Height (m)	Sensor type	Sensor Model	Orientation (°)	Heated
30 m	wind vane	Thies Clima First Class	141°	yes
132 m	wind vane	Thies Clima First Class	137°	no
187 m	wind vane	Thies Clima First Class	135°	yes

Fig. 24 shows the upper 20 or so meters of the 200 m mast with the top anemometer (Thies Clima First Class Advanced). On the left it shows the northwest-booms with two Thies Clima First Class Advanced cup anemometers at 180 m and at 191 m and a METEK uSonic-3 Scientific sonic anemometer at 188 m. On the right it shows the southeast-booms with a Vaisala WAA252 cup anemometer at 180 m, a Thies Clima First Class wind vane at 187 m and a Thies Clima First Class Advanced cup anemometer at 191 m. Fig. 25 to Fig. 29 show close-up examples of the mounting of different wind sensors.

Fig. 24 The upper 20 or so meters of the 200 m mast with top anemometer and with northwest-booms (left) and southeast-booms (right) at 180 m, 188 m and 191 m. Note also the areal marker balls. Photo courtesy of Telecontracting Scandinavia AB

Fig. 25 Thies Clima First Class Advanced cup anemometer at 180 m mounted on a 5.4 m boom

Fig. 26 METEK uSonic-3 Scientific sonic anemometer at 188 m mounted on a 5.4 m boom

Fig. 27 Thies Clima First Class wind vane at 187 m mounted on a 5.4 m boom

Fig. 28 Thies Clima Ultrasonic Anemometer 3D sonic anemometer at 140 m mounted on a 5.4 m boom

Fig. 29 Top anemometer
Thies Clima First Class at 200 m
a) view from below
b) with lightning rod

a)

b)

5.2 140 m mast

Measurement masts

For the NEWA experiment Fraunhofer IEE erected a met mast with a nominal height of 140 m (MM140) upwind of Rödeser Berg early October 2016. Furthermore two scanning lidars (WS1 and WS3) as well as one wind profiler (WP6) were located approximately 70 m northeast to the 140 m mast. The measurement equipment was dismantled at the end of October 2017.

5.2.1 Site description

The surrounding environment is characterized by an agricultural land use. A farming house is located next to the field on which the wind scanner and the 140 m mast were installed.

Fig. 30 360° panorama view of the measurement site of WS1 and WS3 at the 140 m mast (MM140).

Fig. 31 Satellite image of the area surrounding the measurement location of MM140, WS1, WS3 and WP6.
Source: Google Earth

5.2.2 Mast design and instrumentation

The 140 m high mast (type GE-LR 140) consisted of a triangular lattice structure. The trusses (type GM12) had a nominal side length of 0.6 m. The mast was composed of 47 segments, each with a height of 2925 mm. Attached to the top segment was a vertical tube on which the top anemometer was mounted. The mast was installed by Ge:Net in October 2016. The measurements at the mast were completed on 31 October 2017.

The mast was oriented so that the booms could be clamped as extension of the mast face extended normal to the prevailing wind direction. The booms had a length of 3 m and were used as mounts for wind and other meteorological sensors, i. e. cup anemometers, sonic anemometers, air pressure, temperature and relative humidity. The booms were oriented in two directions at about 127° (southeast) and 307° (northwest) to true north, see Fig. 33. The orientation of the booms is given in Tab. 10.

The mast was guyed to six foundations in three directions at 35°, 155° and 275° to true north around the mast base. The two foundations in each direction were about 45 m and 85 m from the mast base. In total 21 guy wires were used at 7 heights. Four aerial marker balls were used at the outer guy wires in each of the three directions.

Fig. 32 shows the view from the ground on the 3 m long booms on the mast. The 140 m tall mast (MM140) was equipped with 11 sonic anemometers and 5 cup anemometers at 9 height levels, see Fig. 33. Tab. 10 provides a complete list of wind sensors installed at the 140 m mast during the NEWA forested hill experiment. The data sheets and calibration reports of the sensors can be found in the Appendix.

The wind sensors were installed at the outer end of the 3 m booms (see Fig. 35 for a drawing of the boom model). In Fig. 34 and Fig. 36 the radiation shields of meteorological sensors that are also mounted on some of the 3 m long booms are

visible. Fig. 36 shows the top anemometer at 140 m above ground. Here an almost undisturbed flow can be assumed because there was no lighting rod installed.

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Measurement masts
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Fig. 32 View from the ground of the 140 m mast (MM140)

Fig. 33 Instrumentation and mast layout of the 140 m tall met mast (MM140), Drawing by DTU Wind Energy modified by Fraunhofer IEE

Height (m)	Sensor type	Sensor model	Sampling frequency (Hz)	Orientation (°)	Heated
10	sonic	Metek Standard USA-1	20 Hz	127	no
20	sonic	Metek Standard USA-1	20 Hz	127	yes
20	sonic	Metek Standard USA-1	20 Hz	307	no
40	sonic	Metek Standard USA-1	20 Hz	127	no
40	cup	Thies Clima First Class Advanced	1 Hz	307	no
60	sonic	Metek Standard USA-1	20 Hz	127	yes
60	sonic	Metek Standard USA-1	20 Hz	307	no
80	sonic	Metek Standard USA-1	20 Hz	127	no
80	cup	Thies Clima First Class Advanced	1 Hz	307	no
100	sonic	Metek Standard USA-1	20 Hz	127	no
100	cup	Thies Clima First Class Advanced	1 Hz	307	no
120	sonic	Metek Standard USA-1	20 Hz	127	no
120	cup	Thies Clima First Class Advanced	1 Hz	307	no
135	sonic	Metek Standard USA-1	20 Hz	127	yes
135	sonic	Metek Standard USA-1	20 Hz	307	no
140	cup	Thies Clima First Class Advanced	1 Hz	307	no

Tab. 10 Wind sensors at the 140 m met mast (MM140) sorted by measurement height

Fig. 34 Instrumentation on the lowest 3 m boom at 10 m of the 140 m mast (MM140) showing radiation shields of air temperature, relative humidity and air pressure sensors as well as a Metek Standard USA-1 sonic anemometer

Fig. 35 Drawing of the boom model used at the 140 m mast (MM140)

Source: DTU Wind Energy

Fig. 36 Photograph of the top end of the 140 m mast (MM140) showing the highest booms with two Metek Standard USA-1 sonic anemometers at 135 m and the top cup anemometer (Thies Clima First Class Advanced) at 140 m. Note that there was no lightning rod installed at the top. Photo courtesy of Ge:Net

6 Wind profilers

Several remote sensing wind profilers (labelled WP in Tab. 05 and Tab. 07) were installed during the Kassel Experiment around the measurement site at Rödeser Berg. Their purpose was to collect information about the vertical wind profiles. This section details the measurement sites as well as the configuration of the different wind profilers. During the Kassel Experiment four lidar profilers (WP1, WP3, WP4 and WP6) and two sodar profilers (WP2 and WP5) were installed. The data availability of the lidar and sodar wind profiler measurements at 135 m measurement height above ground is shown in Fig. 17.

Note that due to the measurement principle of lidar profilers there is a measurement error in complex terrain. This is particularly true for lidar profilers placed e. g. at the top of a hill. The error is dependent on the flow shape above the measurement site and varies with wind direction (compare Klaas et. al 2015).

In case of the NEWA forested hill experiment Kassel this might be relevant for WP3. For this site the terrain induced deviations between the lidar and a measurement mast were simulated according to the methodology outlined in Klaas et. al 2015 using the flow model Meteodyn WT version 5.3.2. The lidar error in the horizontal wind speed was estimated to be in the order of 1 % for the main flow transect which is negligible for example for flow model validations. It reaches 2 % to 3 % for south-eastern and north-western winds. Correction factors are available in the appendix.

6.1 WP1

WP1 is one of the lidar profilers which was located along the main measurement transect. The device marks the north-eastern end of the transect. The north-eastern part of the transect is also probed by multi-lidar and RHI scans (see also Fig. 09 and Fig. 15). WP1 is a Leosphere Windcube v2 which was mounted on a trailer and powered by a methanol fuel cell (Fig. 37). The vicinity of the surrounding terrain is characterised by agricultural land use and mainly open fields. East of the measurement location a small group of trees can be found (Fig. 38).

WP1 was configured to simultaneously measure at 10 heights. On 2016-10-20 some of the heights were changed to also be able to sample higher up into the atmosphere. The instrument is configured to emit 30,000 pulses per second and 20,000 pulses are accumulated to derive a single radial velocity. Five beam directions are sampled. The half opening angle is 28° and the azimuth difference between the beam orientations is 90° . Also, the vertical beam direction is sampled. Together with the internal mechanics this results in a measurement frequency of approximately 1.25 Hz and an independent sample of the wind vector is available every approximately 4 s (Tab. 11).

Type	S/N	Nominal measurement heights* (m)	Measurement frequency	Time to sample complete profile
Leosphere Wincube v2	#164	2016/09/02 to 2016/10/20 06:30 40, 58, 78, 98, 118, 133, 138, 158, 178, 198 2016/10/20 06:40 to end of campaign 40, 58, 78, 98, 118, 133, 158, 198, 248, 290	approx. 1.25 Hz	approx. 4 s

Tab. 11 Details of the measurement of WP1; * Please note that the lidar was operated on a trailer and 2 m should be added to the measurement heights to get the height above ground.

Fig. 37 Trailer of WP1 including solar panels; PTH sensor and network antenna.

Fig. 38 360° panorama view of the measurement site of WP1.

Fig. 39 Satellite image of the area surrounding the measurement location of WP1. Source: Google Earth

6.2 WP2

Wind profilers

WP2 was located west of Rödeser Berg. WP2 is a Vaisala Triton Sodar which uses a phased array to emit a chirp into three directions at a frequency of approx. 4500 Hz. The system was powered by a PV-Battery-System. The close surroundings are characterized by open farm land. Several hundred meters to the west and to the north small areas of forest can be found. WP2 was measuring at 10 different heights between 40 m and 200 m above ground level.

Type	S/N	Measurement heights (m)	Measurement frequency	Time to sample complete profile
Vaisala Triton	#358	40, 50, 60, 80, 100, 120, 140, 160, 180, 200	approx. 0.5 Hz	approx. 6 s

Tab. 01 Details of the measurement of WP2.

Fig. 40 Setup of WP2 including solar panels.

Fig. 41 360° panorama view of the measurement site of WP2.
date: 2016-08-01

Fig. 42 Satellite image of the area surrounding the measurement location of WP2.
Source: Google Earth

6.3 WP3

WP3 was located at the south-eastern border of Rödeser Berg and located on the transect, which is probed by the multi-lidar and RHI scans (comp. Fig. 09). WP3 is a Leosphere Windcube v1 which was installed close to an old farm house. The power supply is provided directly from the grid. The direct vicinity of the measurement location is dominated by the buildings of the farm house which are 2.5 stories high and forest with tall trees. WP3 was configured to measure 10 measurement heights simultaneously.

Type	S/N	Measurement heights (m)	Measurement frequency	Time to sample complete profile
Leosphere Windcube v1	#72	40, 60, 80, 100, 120, 135, 160, 200, 250, 300	approx. 1 Hz	approx. 4 s

Tab. 12 Details of the measurement of WP3.

Tab. 13 Lidar errors due to complex flow for profiling lidar WP3 in percent. The lidar errors were estimated with Meteodyn WT 64 bit version 5.3.2. To correct the lidar measured wind speed multiply the raw data values of the wind speed by $(E/100)+1$ with E being the lidar error given in the table.

	Measurement height (m)									
	40	60	80	100	120	135	160	200	250	300
10	0.7	1.1	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.0	-	-
20	0.7	1.2	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.0	-	-	-	-
30	1.2	1.2	0.1	0.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
40	1.5	0.4	0.3	0.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
50	1.3	1.4	0.1	0.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
60	1.0	1.0	0.8	0.2	0.0	-	-	-	-	-
70	1.0	1.0	0.8	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.0	-	-	-
80	1.0	0.9	1.0	0.8	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.2	-	-
90	1.0	0.9	1.0	1.1	0.9	1.0	0.9	0.7	0.6	0.3
100	1.1	1.1	1.2	1.2	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.3	1.0	0.8
110	1.5	1.4	1.5	1.7	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.7	1.4	1.2
120	1.6	1.4	1.5	1.5	1.8	1.9	1.9	1.9	1.7	1.5
130	1.7	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.8	1.9	2.0	1.9	1.8	1.6
140	2.2	1.5	1.4	1.6	1.8	1.7	1.8	1.8	1.7	1.5
150	2.1	1.9	1.3	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.3	1.1
160	1.9	1.9	1.2	1.3	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.1	1.0	0.9
170	1.6	1.7	1.1	1.0	1.0	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.6	0.5
180	1.5	1.5	0.8	0.7	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.0	-	-
190	1.2	0.9	0.2	0.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
200	0.9	0.7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
210	0.9	0.4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
220	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
230	1.1	0.8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
240	1.3	1.0	0.7	0.3	0.1	0.0	-	-	-	-
250	1.9	1.5	1.1	0.9	0.7	0.5	0.3	0.0	-	-
260	1.8	1.6	1.7	1.3	1.0	0.8	0.8	0.4	0.1	-
270	2.3	2.3	2.1	2.1	2.0	2.0	1.8	1.4	1.1	0.6
280	2.4	2.5	2.3	2.3	2.4	2.4	2.3	2.0	1.5	1.1
290	2.5	2.6	2.7	2.8	2.8	2.8	2.7	2.4	2.1	1.7
300	2.4	2.4	2.5	2.5	2.8	2.9	2.8	2.6	2.3	2.0
310	2.3	2.3	2.3	2.3	2.6	2.7	2.7	2.6	2.4	2.1
320	2.9	2.1	2.0	2.2	2.4	2.4	2.4	2.4	2.2	2.0
330	2.6	2.5	1.6	1.8	1.9	1.9	2.0	1.9	1.8	1.7
340	1.9	2.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.4	1.3
350	1.1	1.7	1.0	1.0	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.0	1.0	0.9
360	0.8	1.5	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.2	0.3

Fig. 43 Setup of WP3 at the farm house close to Elmershausen.

Fig. 44 360° panorama view of the measurement site of WP3

Fig. 45 Satellite images of the area surrounding the measurement location of WP3,
a): zoomed in
b): overview
Source: Google Earth

a)

b)

6.4 WP4

WP4 was located south-west of Rödeser Berg. WP4 is a ZephIR ZP300 lidar profiler. The power supply was provided directly from the grid. The unit was installed at a biogas power plant on top of a small electrical substation (approximately 2 m height), see Fig. 46.

Please note that the biogas power plant is currently not visible in the satellite pictures from Google Earth (Fig. 48), as it yet was not installed when the pictures were taken. There are several taller buildings in the direct vicinity of the lidar. The surroundings are then dominated by fields. The measurement device is configured for measuring 11 measurement heights. Due to the fact that the continuous wave lidar has to focus at each configured measurement height independently, the heights were measured one after another. Because the unit was installed at 2 m height and 1 m has to be added to the measurement height by default, 3 m have to be added to the nominal measurement height in order to obtain the measurement height above ground.

Type	Serial number	Nominal measurement heights (m)*	Measurement frequency	Time to sample complete profile
ZephIR ZP300	#317	37, 38, 39, 57, 77, 117, 137, 157, 197, 247, 297	approx. 50 Hz	approx. 15 s

Tab. 14 Details of the measurement of WP4. *By default one meter height has to be added to the measurement height (device height). Here, additionally 2 m have to be added in order to account for the installation on the substation.

Fig. 46 Setup of WP4 on top a small substation that has a height of approx. 2 m. In the background the biogas reactor can be seen.

Fig. 47 360° panorama view of the measurement site of WP4.

Fig. 48 Satellite image of the area surrounding the measurement location of WP4. Note that the biogas plant was not erected when the satellite photos were taken. Source: Google Earth

6.5 WP5

WP5 was located approx. 5 km Northeast of Rödeser Berg. The position of WP5 lies on the extension of the transect line about 3 km northeast of WP1 (compare Fig. 09). The sodar wind profiler (type AQ500 WindFinder) was installed on a forest-clearing. Between 50 m and 200 m, it measures the wind speed for every 5 m at a measurement frequency of 0.5 Hz. In the course of the experiment (long-term campaign) the wind farm Escheberg consisting of 4 turbines was constructed near the measurement site of WP5. Tab. 03 and Tab. 04 provide details about the locations, the specifications and the construction of the wind turbines. Another two wind turbines are planned to be erected in wind farm Escheberg.

Type	Serial number	Measurement heights (m)	Measurement frequency	Time to sample complete profile
AQ500 Sodar	AJ03	50, 55, 60, 65, 70, 75, 80, 85, 90, 95, 100, 105, 110, 115, 120, 125, 130, 135, 140, 145, 150, 155, 160, 165, 170, 175, 180, 185, 190, 195, 200	approx. 0.5 Hz	approx. 6 s

Tab. 15 Details of the measurement of WP5.

Fig. 49 Setup of WP5.

Fig. 50 Satellite image of the area surrounding the measurement location of WP5. The turquoise dots indicate the locations of the wind turbines which were erected during the measurement campaign. Source: Google Earth

Fig. 51 360° panorama view from the site of WP5.

6.6 WP6

The tall wind profiler WP6 (Nickname »Alize«) was installed close to the 140 m mast directly next to the two scanning lidars WS1 and WS3. Therefore, the panorama pictures, satellite image and site description from the 140 m mast site are also representative for this profiler, see section 5.2.1, Fig. 30 and Fig. 31. The power supply for Alize was coming from the grid.

WP6 is a Leosphere Windcube WLS70 which was designed to measure up to great heights due to an enhanced laser power. For this experiment the measurement heights were programmed from 100 m to 200 m, every 20 m; 200 m to 1000 m, every 50 m; 1000 m to 2000 m, every 100 m, see Tab. 07.

Tab. 16 Details of the measurement of WP5.

Type	Serial number	Nominal measurement heights (m)	Measurement frequency	Time to sample complete profile
Leosphere Windcube WLS70	Alize	100, 120, 140, 160, 180, 200, 250 300, 350, 400, 450, 500, 550, 600, 650, 700, 750, 800, 850, 900, 950, 1000 1100, 1200, 1300, 1400, 1500, 1600, 1700, 1800, 1900, 2000	approx. 1 Hz	approx. 4 s

Fig. 52 Picture of WP6 (centre) next to WS1 and WS3 at the anchoring of the 140 m mast.

7 Scanning lidars

Scanning lidars

Nine scanning lidars/WindScanners (WS) were installed as part of the NEWA forested hill experiment Kassel. Details of the individual WindScanners and their configurations are given in Tab. 17. Four of these (WS4 and WS5, WS7 and WS8) performed multi-lidar scans along the transect (see Fig. 58). The other scanners performed either RHI or PPI scans. The data availability is shown in Fig. 53.

Type	Serial number	Scan patterns	Accumulation time	FFT points	Pulse length	Sector	
						Elevation angle	Azimuth angle
WS1	#12	RHI	1000 ms	128	Long	0.25° – 13.76°	36.92°
WS2	#23	RHI	1000 ms	128	Long	-13.76° – -0.24°	37.10°
WS3	#57	PPI	1000 ms	128	Long	5.60°	0° – 360°
WS4	#13	CT	1000 ms	128	Long	-	-
WS5	#24	CT	1000 ms	128	Long	-	-
WS6	#58	RHI	1000 ms	128	Long	0.24° – 13.76°	37.10°
WS7	#59	CT	1000 ms	128	Long	-	-
WS8	#07	CT	1000 ms	128	Long	-	-
WS9	#17	PPI	1000 ms	128	Long	6.78°	14.49° – 35.51°

Tab. 17 Details of the scanning lidar measurements

Fig. 53 Data availability of the WindScanners, sorted in terms of the respective scan patterns. In periods of lacking availability, either no data was collected or the WindScanners performed a different scan pattern as originally intended.

7.1 RHI-Scans

Three scanning lidars were performing RHI-Scans along the measurement transect. One scanning lidar (WS1) which was located next to the 140 m mast was measuring the wind approaching the Rödeser Berg. The other two lidars (WS2, WS6) located atop the hill were measuring downwind from the 200 m mast. Fig. 54 shows the overall configuration of the RHI-Scan.

Fig. 54 Measurement configuration of RHI-Scans.
Note that the given angles of the RHI scans are approximate values and slightly differ from the measurement data.

7.1.1 WS1

WS1 was located at the site of the 140 m mast. For a site description of the immediate surroundings of WS 1 see section 5.2.1. WS1 was configured to perform repeating RHI-scans of the flow approaching the Rödeser Berg along the measurement transect.

The measurement range was 3.500 m reaching up to the position of the 200 m mast. The elevation angle was changed from about 0° to 14° . WS1 was operating in sweeping mode (measuring while moving) with a speed of 0.5° per second. The elevation angle for each interval is stored with the mean elevation (e. g. 0.24° for the interval from 0° to 0.5°).

Fig. 55 Picture of the measurement site of WS1 (center), WS3 (right) and WP6 (back left) at the north-eastern anchoring of the 140 m mast, line of sight towards south-west.

7.1.2 WS2

WS2 was located next to the 200 m mast on Rödeser Berg. For pictures and information about the environment see section 5.1.1. WS2 was configured to perform repeating RHI-scans of the flow downwind the Rödeser Berg along the measurement transect.

The measurement range was 2.000 m reaching up to the position of WP1. The elevation angle was changed from about -14° to 0° . The lidar is operating in sweeping mode (measuring while moving) with a speed of 0.5° per second. The elevation angle for each interval is stored with the mean elevation (e. g. -0.24° for the interval from -0.5° to 0°).

Fig. 56 Picture of the installation of WS2 on top of a container at the 200 m mast at Rödeser Berg.

7.1.3 WS6

WS6 was located next to the 200 m mast on Rödeser Berg. For pictures and information about the environment see section 3.

WS6 was configured to perform repeating RHI-Scans of the flow downwind the Rödeser Berg along the measurement transect. The measurement range was 2.000 m reaching up to the position of WP1. The elevation angle was changed from about 0° to 15° .

7.2 PPI-Scans

Two scanning lidars were performing PPI-Scans of the wind approaching the Rödeser Berg from west and southwest (see Fig. 57).

Fig. 57 Schematic illustration of the two PPI-scans by WS3 (yellow) and WS9 (red). The red circles indicate the range of 5000 m which is maximum measurement range programmed for both devices. Source: Google Earth

7.2.1 WS3

WS3 was located at the site of the 140 m mast. For a site description see section 5.2.1. It was configured to measure full repeating PPI-scans from 0° to 360° with a range of 5000 m with an elevation angle of 5.6° . The lidar was operating in sweeping mode (measuring while moving) with a speed of 2° per second. The azimuth angle for each interval is stored with the mean azimuth (e. g. 1° for the interval from 0° to 2°).

7.2.2 WS9

WS9 is located west of the Rödeser Berg next to WS5 at the wind turbine V47-WT1 (see Fig. 08). For pictures and information about the environment see 7.3.2. WS9 was configured to measure full repeating PPI-scans from 15° to 135° with a range of 5000 m with an elevation angle of 6.78°. The lidar was operating in sweeping mode (measuring while moving) with a speed of 2° per second. The azimuth angle for each interval is stored with the mean azimuth (e. g. 16° for the interval from 15° to 17°).

Scanning lidars

7.3 Multi-lidar scans

Four of the nine scanning lidars performed pairwise multi-lidar scans. The measurements were performed along a line, which crosses the position of the two measurement masts in the experiment. Their positions can be seen in Fig. 58. Along the scan line, several positions are scanned in step-stare mode. These positions are also indicated in Fig. 58 (indicated by ML X). For each point two heights were scanned (60 m and 135 m above the ground). In addition to that, at two positions data was also collected at 400 m and 600 m in order to gain information about the wind conditions in greater heights (see Fig. 59).

Fig. 58 Locations of multi-lidar measurements ("ML"): Measurements ML 1 to ML 6 southwest of the 200 m met mast (MM200) were performed by WS 4 and WS 5. Measurements ML 7 to ML 11 northeast of MM200 were performed by WS 7 and WS 8. Source: Google Earth

Fig. 59 Measurements heights of the multi-lidar scans along the scan line/transect

**7.3.1
WS4**

WS4 was located southwest of the Rödeser Berg at a gas decompression station. The small one-level substation is surrounded by agricultural land use.

Scanning lidars

Fig. 60 Picture of WS4 next to a small gas decompression station.

Fig. 61 360° panorama view of the measurement site of WS4.

7.3.2 WS5

WS5 was located west of the Rödeser Berg at the foot of wind turbine V47-WT1 (see Fig. 08). The wind turbine is surrounded by agricultural land-use. A small group of bushes and small trees is located right next to the turbine.

Fig. 62 Picture of the installation of WS5 and WS9 right next to the wind turbine V47-WT1.

Fig. 63 360° panorama view of the measurement site of WS5 and WS9 at the wind turbine V47-WT1.

7.3.3 WS7

WS7 was located in the north of Rödeser Berg next to a small electrical transformer station in a slightly sloping area. The area surrounding WS7 is predominantly agricultural land. There are residential houses and some trees in the immediate vicinity.

.....
Scanning lidars
.....
Fig. 64 Picture of the installed scanning lidar WS7 with the Rödeser Berg and MM200 in the background.

Fig. 65 360° panorama view of the measurement site of WS7

7.3.4
WS8

Scanning lidars

WS8 is located west of the Rödeser Berg next to a small one-level electrical substation close to railway tracks.

Fig. 66 Picture of WS8 next to a small single-story railway building and railway tracks.

Fig. 67 360° panorama view of the measurement site of WS8

8 References

Freier, Julia (2017): Approaches to characterise forest structures for wind resource assessment using airborne laser scan data. Master thesis. Kassel University, Kassel. Department of Mechanical Engineering.

GeoBasis-DE (2012): CORINE Land Cover 10ha. CLC10 (2012). Leipzig: Bundesamt für Kartographie und Geodäsie. Available online at www.geodatenzentrum.de.

Klaas, Tobias; Pauscher, Lukas; Callies, Doron (2015): LiDAR-mast deviations in complex terrain and their simulation using CFD. In *metz* 24 (6), pp. 591–603. DOI: 10.1127/metz/2015/0637.

Mann, J.; Angelou, N.; Arnqvist, J.; Callies, D.; Cantero, E.; Arroyo, R. Chávez et al. (2017): Complex terrain experiments in the New European Wind Atlas. In *Philosophical transactions. Series A, Mathematical, physical, and engineering sciences* 375 (2017). DOI: 10.1098/rsta.2016.0101.

Pauscher, Lukas; Callies, Doron; Klaas, Tobias; Foken, Thomas (2017): Wind observations from a forested hill. Relating turbulence statistics to surface characteristics in hilly and patchy terrain. In *metz*. DOI: 10.1127/metz/2017/0863.

Pauscher, Lukas; Vasiljevic, Nikola; Callies, Doron; Lea, Guillaume; Mann, Jakob; Klaas, Tobias et al. (2016): An Inter-Comparison Study of Multi- and DBS Lidar Measurements in Complex Terrain. In *Remote Sensing* 8 (9), p. 782. DOI: 10.3390/rs8090782.

Telecon (2012): Wind Measurement Mast - Site: Rödeser Berg 200 m. Edited by Niclas Östmann. Telecon. Motala, Sweden.

9 Appendix

9.1 Additional information 200 m mast

Wind Measurement Mast: Wolfhagen 200 m. Telecon 2012: Östman, N.,
Telecontracting Scandinavia AB, Motala Sweden

Spec sheets

Thies Clima Wind Cup Anemometer First Class
Vaisala Heated Cup Anemometer WAA252
Thies Clima Wind Vane First Class

Thies Clima Ultrasonic Anemometer 3D
Gill Ultrasonic Anemometer HS 50
Metek Ultrasonic Wind Sensor uSonic 3 Class A

Thies Clima Air Pressure Transmitter
Wilmers Temperature Sensor 0445
Wilmers Temperatur / humidity Sensor 0535

9.2 Additional information 140 m mast

Spec Sheets

Thies Clima Wind Cup Anemometer First Class
Metek Ultrasonic Wind Sensor uSonic 3 Scientific

Vaisala Barometer PTB110
Vaisala Humidity and Temperature Probe HMP155
PR Electronics Temperature Transmitter 5331A

9.3 Additional information wind profilers

Spec Sheets

Leosphere LIDAR Remote Sensor Windcube V1
Leosphere LIDAR Remote Sensor Windcube V2
ZephIR Wind LIDAR ZR300
AQ Systems Sodar System AQ500 Windfinder
Vaisala SODAR Triton Wind Profiler

9.4 Additional information scanning Lidars

Spec Sheets

Leosphere Scanning Lidar Windcube 200s

Wind Measurement Mast

Wind measurement system installed by Telecon conforms with IEC 61400-12-1

Site: Wolfhagen 200m
Customer: Fraunhofer

Issued by: Niclas Östman
Date: 16/03/2012

Content:

1. Site map
2. Mast drawing
3. Sensorlevel page1
4. Sensorlevel page2
5. Sensorlevel page3
6. Boom heights
7. Guy wire
8. Mast foundation
9. Guy wire foundation
10. Cue Dee K600
11. Cue Dee K1050
12. Telecon folding boom 5400mm
13. Telecon folding boom GIL sonic
14. Telecon Top Spire

Mast Coordinates WGS 84:
 Latitude: 51.36650
 Longitude: 9.19479

	Wind Measurement Mast	
	Site: Wolfshagen 200m	
Issued by: Niclas Östman	FILNAMN WIND MEASUREMENT MAST WOLFHAGEN 200M 16032012.VSD	REV A
Date: 2012-03-16	SCALE	Page 2 of 15

Wind Measurement Mast

Obstruction light:

- 3pcs 190m
- 3pcs 155m
- 3pcs 110m
- 3pcs 65m

Guy wire:

Nr	Height	Dimension
#10	193m	185mm ²
#9	180m	135mm ² Torsion
#8	160m	185mm ²
#7	140m	185mm ²
#6	120m	185mm ²
#5	100m	135mm ²
#4	80m	135mm ²
#3	60m	105mm ²
#2	40m	105mm ²
#1	20m	105mm ²

Misc:

K600 (25mm) Red:	194-196m
K1050 (50mm) Red:	180-194m
K1050 (50mm) White:	166-180m
K1050 (50mm) Red:	160-166m
K1050 (60mm) Red:	152-160m
K1050 (60mm) White:	138-152m
K1050 (60mm) Red:	124-138m
K1050 (60mm) Zink:	0-124m

Mast Painting:

Red RAL3021, White RAL 9016

Ball markers guywire 16pcs

Field index datalogger:
[ww-Sensorliste.pdf](#) 23/02/2012

	Wind Measurement Mast	
	Site: Wolfshagen 200m	
Issued by: Niclas Östman	FILNAMN	REV
Date: 2012-03-16	WIND MEASUREMENT MAST WOLFHAGEN 200M 16032012.VSD	A
SCALE	Page	3 of 15

Mast Top View

	Wind Measurement Mast	
	Site: Wolfshagen 200m	
Issued by: Niclas Östman	FILNAMN WIND MEASUREMENT MAST WOLFHAGEN 200M 16032012.VSD	REV A
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Mast Top View

	Wind Measurement Mast	
	Site: Wolfshagen 200m	
Issued by: Niclas Östman	FILNAMN WIND MEASUREMENT MAST WOLFHAGEN 200M 16032012.VSD	REV A
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Mast Top View

	Wind Measurement Mast	
	Site: Wolfshagen 200m	
Issued by: Niclas Östman	FILNAMN WIND MEASUREMENT MAST WOLFHAGEN 200M 16032012.VSD	REV A
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Boom Heights

	FRAMTAGEN AV Niclas Östman	DATUM 2012-01-24	DOK NR KP:004	REV A	SIDA 1
	DOKUMENTANSVARIG LARS LAURIN	INFORMATIONSKLASS ALLMÄNN			
	REFERENSDOKUMENT INSTALLATIONSFORMULÄR, FOTOANVISNING, MASTRITNING, EGE MARK				

Boom heights

Site: <u>WME Wolfhagen</u>	Date: <u>14/03/2012</u>
Customer: <u>Fraunhofer</u>	Sign: <u>Niclas Östman</u>
Mast type: <u>Cue Dee K1050</u>	
Height: <u>200m</u>	Temp: <u>+5</u>

Reference document:

Cue Dee K1050 drawing "CD455020"

Height per section: 200 cm

Height guy frame 10 cm

Height foot: 3 cm

Measurement tool: Tumstock

Measurement performed by: Johanness Kwauka

Sensor No	No of sections	No of guy frames	Boom section height	Total height	Comments
7	19	1	53	3863	
8	14	1	76	2886	
9	9	0	79	1879	
10	9	0	80	1880	
11	4	0	76	876	
28	14	1	77	2887	
25	19	1	177	3987	
19	29	2	61	5881	
17	29	2	61	5881	
16	39	3	79	7909	
21	39	3	32	7862	
6	49	4	59	9899	
24	49	4	143	9983	
14	59	5	39	11889	
15	59	5	38	11888	
26	65	6	38	13098	
5	66	6	132	13392	
23	67	6	46	13506	
20	69	6	28	13888	
3	79	7	18	15888	
4	79	7	17	15887	
13	88	10	191	17891	
18	88	10	191	17891	
27	92	10	99	18599	
22	93	10	191	18891	
1	94	10	106	19006	
2	94	10	103	19003	
12	98	12	214	19934	Top spire inserted 86cm in top section

	Wind Measurement Mast	
	Site: Wolfshagen 200m	
Issued by: Niclas Östman	FILNAMN WIND MEASUREMENT MAST WOLFHAGEN 200M 16032012.VSD	REV A
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Mast View from above

	Wind Measurement Mast	
	Site: Wolfshagen 200m	
Issued by: Niclas Östman	FILNAMN WIND MEASUREMENT MAST WOLFHAGEN 200M 16032012.VSD	REV A
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K1050 Foundation

	Wind Measurement Mast	
	Site: Wolfshagen 200m	
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Guy wire Foundation

For further info, please see :
 Schall- und Bewehrungsplan Seilfundament 1+2+3
 12.08.2011

	Wind Measurement Mast	
	Site: Wolfshagen 200m	
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Cue Dee K600

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	WELDING PER EN ISO 1560-AE HOT DIP GALVANIZED PER EN ISO 1461	CHECKED: 2011-01-27	M.L	ART. NO. CD 431170 Market	REV 4933
	MATERIAL: PROFILE: VARMSÄLVANISERAD	SCALE: 1:12.5	WEIGHT: 75,40 kg	SHEET 1 OF 1	
	FILE NAME: C:\na\Design\Check\K600\CD-431170-Market.dwg				

	Wind Measurement Mast	
	Site: Wolfshagen 200m	
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Cue Dee K1050

	Wind Measurement Mast	
	Site: Wolfshagen 200m	
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Telecon Folding Boom 5400mm

Telecon folding boom

Material: Aluminium (EN6063-T6, EN6082-T6)
 Length: 5400mm
 Weight: 27,5 kg (Complete folding boom)

All measurements are defined in millimeter

	Wind Measurement Mast	
	Site: Wolfshagen 200m	
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Telecon Folding Boom 5400mm for Gill HS-50

All measurements are defined in meter

	Wind Measurement Mast	
	Site: Wolfshagen 200m	
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Telecon Top spire with Lightning rod

	Wind Measurement Mast	
	Site: Wolfshagen 200m	
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WIND

Wind Transmitter "First Class" Advanced

Part number: 4.3351.00.xxx

Special characters are a defined and optimised, dynamic behaviour also at high turbulence intensity, minimal over-speeding, and a low starting value. The measuring value is available at the output as analogue signal and as rectangular digital signal.

For winter operation the instrument (4 .3351 .00 .xxx) is equipped with an electronically regulated heating.

Specification

Part number: 4.3351.00.xxx

Wind speed	
Measuring range	0.3 ... 75 m/s
Accuracy	< 1 % of meas. value (0.3 ... 50 m/s) or < ±0.2 m/s
Linearity	r > 0.99999 (4 ... 20 m/s)
Delay distance	< 3 m (aac. to ASTM D 5096-96)
Data output digital	
Frequency	1082 Hz at 50 m/s
Operating voltage	
Electronic	3.3 ... 48 V DC 130 µA from 3,3 ... 15 V 180 µA > 15 V
Heating	24 V AC/DC, max 25 W
General	
Ambient temp.	-50 ... +80 °C
Electr. connection	8 pol. plug connection
Mounting	onto mast tube Ø 1''
Protection	IP 55
Survival speed	80 m/s (min. 30 minutes)
Weight	0.5 kg
Fixing boring	Ø 35 x 25 mm
Material housing	aluminium, anodised

Material cup star	carbon-fiber glass reinforced
-------------------	-------------------------------

Versions

As per 4.3351.00.xxx, but:

Product number 4.3351.00.140

Data output digital	
Sink Output	1 ... 250 mA
Source Output	1 ... 100 mA
Data output analog	
Wind speed	0 ... 20 mA (0 ... 75 m/s)

Product number 4.3351.00.141

Data output digital	
Sink Output	1 ... 250 mA
Source Output	1 ... 100 mA
Data output analog	
Wind speed	4 ... 20 mA (0 ... 75 m/s)

Product number 4.3351.00.161

Data output digital	
Sink Output	1 ... 250 mA
Source Output	1 ... 100 mA
Data output analog	
Wind speed	0 ... 10 V (0 ... 75 m/s)

Product number 4.3351.00.173

Data output digital	
Sink Output	1 ... 250 mA
Source Output	1 ... 100 mA
Data output analog	
Wind speed	0 ... 5 V (0 ... 75 m/s)

Accessories

Product	Product name	Brief description
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	<p>Traverse for Wind Transmitters "First Class" 4.3174.00.000</p>	<p>For mounting the wind speed transmitter and wind direction transmitter jointly onto a mast.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2">General</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Height</td> <td>0.76 m</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Mounting</td> <td>on mast tube Ø 1,5"</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Material</td> <td>aluminium, anodised (AlMgSi0.5)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Sensor distance horizontal</td> <td>0.6 m</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Sensor distance vertikal</td> <td>0.2 m</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Weight</td> <td>3 kg</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Fixing boring</td> <td>Ø 34 mm for First Class wind sensors</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	General		Height	0.76 m	Mounting	on mast tube Ø 1,5"	Material	aluminium, anodised (AlMgSi0.5)	Sensor distance horizontal	0.6 m	Sensor distance vertikal	0.2 m	Weight	3 kg	Fixing boring	Ø 34 mm for First Class wind sensors
General																		
Height	0.76 m																	
Mounting	on mast tube Ø 1,5"																	
Material	aluminium, anodised (AlMgSi0.5)																	
Sensor distance horizontal	0.6 m																	
Sensor distance vertikal	0.2 m																	
Weight	3 kg																	
Fixing boring	Ø 34 mm for First Class wind sensors																	
	<p>Hanger 1m First Class 4.3184.01.000</p>	<p>The hanger is used for the lateral mounting of a wind transmitter, First Class type, onto a mast</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2">General</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Length</td> <td>1 m</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Mounting</td> <td>at mast tube Ø 40 ... 80 mm</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Material</td> <td>aluminium (AlMgSi0.5)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Weight</td> <td>1.5 kg</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Fixing boring</td> <td>Ø 34 mm</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	General		Length	1 m	Mounting	at mast tube Ø 40 ... 80 mm	Material	aluminium (AlMgSi0.5)	Weight	1.5 kg	Fixing boring	Ø 34 mm				
General																		
Length	1 m																	
Mounting	at mast tube Ø 40 ... 80 mm																	
Material	aluminium (AlMgSi0.5)																	
Weight	1.5 kg																	
Fixing boring	Ø 34 mm																	

WA25 Wind Set for Arctic Conditions

Features/Benefits

- Non-freezing, high-performance wind set
- Cups and vane, sensor bodies and bearings are heated to prevent snow buildup and ice formation
- Accurate wind speed and direction measurement
- Low measurement starting threshold
- Conical anemometer cups provide excellent linearity

The WA25 resists snow build-up and ice formation. The result is accurate wind measurement in cold environments.

The Vaisala Wind Set WA25 is a high-quality cup and vane wind measurement station designed for arctic conditions.

The WA25 consists of a Vaisala Anemometer WAA252, a Vaisala Wind Vane WAV252, an optional crossarm, a power supply and cabling.

Heating provides resistance to snow and ice

Most of the heating power is consumed where it is needed most – in the cups and vane. Foil heaters, integrated into the cups and vane, prevent snow buildup and ice formation.

Heating power is also supplied to the sensor shafts, bearings and bodies. This keeps the sensor bodies free of ice, which is important for maintaining the aerodynamic performance.

Anemometer with excellent linearity

The WAA252 is a fast-response, low-threshold anemometer. Three

lightweight, conical cups mounted on the cup wheel, provide excellent linearity over the entire operating range, up to 75 m/s.

A wind-rotated chopper disc attached to the shaft of the cup wheel cuts an infrared light beam 14 times per revolution. This generates a pulse output from a phototransistor.

The output pulse rate is directly proportional to wind speed (e.g., 246 Hz = 24.6 m/s). However, for the highest accuracy, the characteristic transfer function should be used to compensate for starting inertia. (See technical data.)

Sensitive wind vane

The WAV252 is a counterbalanced, low threshold, optoelectronic wind vane. Infrared LEDs and phototransistors are mounted on six orbits on each side of a 6-bit GRAY-coded disc. Turned by the vane, the disc creates changes in the code received by the phototransistors. The output code resolution is $\pm 2.8^\circ$.

Complete package available

The anemometer and vane are designed to be mounted on Vaisala crossarms.

The WHP25 power supply provides the needed operating and heating power for the WA25. The power supply, as well as the signal and power cables are available as options.

The WHP25 power supply provides the operating and heating power needed by the WA25.

Technical Data

Vaisala Anemometer WAA252

Wind speed

Measurement range	0.4...75 m/s
Starting threshold	< 0.5 m/s *
Distance constant	3.4 m
Transfer function	$U = 0.39 + 0.10 \times R$ (where U = wind speed [m/s], R = output pulse rate [Hz])
Accuracy (within range 0.4...60 m/s)	
with characteristic transfer function	± 0.17 m/s **
with transfer function $U = 0.1 \times R$	± 0.5 m/s

General

Transducer output level	
with Iout < +5 mA	high state > 11V
with Iout > -5 mA	low state < 2V
Operating power supply	$U_{in} = 24$ VDC $\pm 10\%$, max. 3.2 A
Typical power consumption ($U_{in} = 24$ VDC)	72 W below +2 °C (+36 °F) (heating on) 1 W above +6 °C (+43 °F) (heating off)
Plug	MIL-C-26482 type
Recommended connector at cable end	SOURIAU MS3116F10-6P
Operating temperature	-55...+55 °C (-67...+131 °F)
Storage temperature	-60...+70 °C (-76...+158 °F)
Material	
housing	AlMgSi, grey&black anodized
cups	PA, reinforced with glassfibre
Dimensions	264 (h) \times 90 (Ø) mm
Swept radius of cup wheel	91 mm
Weight	800 g

Test compliance

Wind tunnel tests	ASTM standard method D5096-90 (for starting threshold, distance constant, transfer function)
Exploratory vibration test	MIL-STD-167-1
Humidity test	MIL-STD-810E, Method 507.3
Salt fog test	MIL-STD-810E, Method 509.3

Complies with EMC standard EN61326-1:1997 + Am1:1998 + Am2:2001; Generic Environment

* Measured with cup wheel in position least favoured by flow direction. Optimum position gives approx. 0.35 m/s threshold.

** Standard Deviation

Vaisala Wind Vane WAV252

Wind direction

Measurement range	0...360°
Starting threshold	< 0.4 m/s
Resolution	$\pm 2.8^\circ$
Damping ratio	0.23
Overshoot ratio	0.47
Delay distance	< 0.5 m
Accuracy	better than $\pm 3^\circ$

General

Operating power supply	24 VDC $\pm 10\%$, max. 2.1 A
Typical power consumption ($U_{in} = 24$ VDC)	50 W below +2 °C (+36 °F) (heating on) 1 W above +6 °C (+43 °F) (heating off)
Output code	6-bit parallel GRAY
Output levels	
With Iout < +3 mA	high state > 11V
With Iout > -3 mA	low state < 2V
Plug	MIL-C-26482 type
Recommended connector at cable end	SOURIAU MS3116F12-10P
Operating temperature	-55...+55 °C (-67...+131 °F)
Storage temperature	-60...+70 °C (-76...+158 °F)
Material	
housing	AlMgSi, grey&black anodized
vane	carbon fibre + glassfibre
Dimensions	355 (h) \times 90 (Ø) mm
Swept radius of vane	218 mm
Weight	850 g

Complies with EMC standard EN61326-1:1997 + Am1:1998; Am2:2001; Generic Environment

Test compliance

Wind tunnel tests	ASTM standard method D 5366-93 (for starting threshold, distance constant, transfer function)
Exploratory vibration test	MIL-STD-167-1
Humidity test	MIL-STD-810E, Method 507.3
Salt fog test	MIL-STD-810E, Method 509.3

Vaisala Wind Set WA25 for arctic conditions

Options and accessories

Crossarm and termination box	WAC151
16-lead signal cable	ZZ45048
6-lead power cable	ZZ45049
Crossarm and analog transmitter	WAT12
6-lead cable for signal and power	ZZ45049
Set of bearings and gasket	1664WA
Cup assembly	WA35066
Power supply	WHP25

Specifications subject to change without prior notice.
©Vaisala Oyj

WIND

Wind Direction Transmitter First Class

Part number: 4.3151.00.xxx

Special characters are a defined and optimised, dynamic behaviour as well as:

- High measurement accuracy and resolution
- High damping with small distance constant
- Low starting value
- Low power consumption
- Simple mounting

The measuring value is available at the output as analogue signal. The output signal can be transmitted to display instruments, recording instruments, data loggers as well as to process control systems. For winter operation the instrument (4.3150.00.xxx) is equipped with an electronically regulated heating.

Specification

Part number: 4.3151.00.xxx

Wind direction	
Measuring range	0 ... 360 °
Resolution	0.35 °
Accuracy	1 °
Starting value	< 0.5 m/s at 10 ° acc. to ASTM D 5096-96 < 0.2 m/s at 90 ° acc. to VDI3786 page 2
Distance constant	< 1.8 m acc. to ASTM D 5096-96
Damping ration	> 0.3 acc. to ASTM D 5096-96
Operating voltage	
Electronic	3.3 ... 42 V DC
Current consumption	1.4 mA standby
Heating	24 V AC/DC, 25 W
General	
Ambient temp.	-50 ... +80 °C
Electr. connection	8 pol. plug connection
Mounting	onto mast tube Ø 1''
Material	aluminium, anodised
Protection	IP 55

Dimension	Ø 450 x 410 mm
Weight	0.7 kg
Fixing boring	Ø 35 x 25 mm

Versions

As per 4.3151.00.xxx, but:

Product number 4.3151.00.140

Data output analog	
Wind direction	0 ... 20 mA
Operating voltage	
Electronic	15 ... 24 V DC
Current consumption	approx. 4.5 mA + lout

Product number 4.3151.00.141

Data output analog	
Wind direction	4 ... 20 mA
Operating voltage	
Electronic	15 ... 24 V DC
Current consumption	approx. 4.5 mA + lout

Product number 4.3151.00.161

Data output analog	
Wind direction	0 ... 10 V
Operating voltage	
Electronic	15 ... 24 V DC
Current consumption	approx. 4.5 mA

Product number 4.3151.00.173

Data output analog	
Wind direction	0 ... 5 V
Operating voltage	
Electronic	12 ... 24 V DC
Current consumption	approx. 4.5 mA

Accessories

Product	Product name	Brief description
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	<p>Traverse for Wind Transmitters "First Class" 4.3174.00.000</p>	<p>For mounting the wind speed transmitter and wind direction transmitter jointly onto a mast.</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td colspan="2">General</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Height</td> <td>0.76 m</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Mounting</td> <td>on mast tube Ø 1,5"</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Material</td> <td>aluminium, anodised (AlMgSi0.5)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Sensor distance horizontal</td> <td>0.6 m</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Sensor distance vertikal</td> <td>0.2 m</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Weight</td> <td>3 kg</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Fixing boring</td> <td>Ø 34 mm for First Class wind sensors</td> </tr> </table>	General		Height	0.76 m	Mounting	on mast tube Ø 1,5"	Material	aluminium, anodised (AlMgSi0.5)	Sensor distance horizontal	0.6 m	Sensor distance vertikal	0.2 m	Weight	3 kg	Fixing boring	Ø 34 mm for First Class wind sensors
General																		
Height	0.76 m																	
Mounting	on mast tube Ø 1,5"																	
Material	aluminium, anodised (AlMgSi0.5)																	
Sensor distance horizontal	0.6 m																	
Sensor distance vertikal	0.2 m																	
Weight	3 kg																	
Fixing boring	Ø 34 mm for First Class wind sensors																	
	<p>Hanger 1m First Class 4.3184.01.000</p>	<p>The hanger is used for the lateral mounting of a wind transmitter, First Class type, onto a mast</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td colspan="2">General</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Length</td> <td>1 m</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Mounting</td> <td>at mast tube Ø 40 ... 80 mm</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Material</td> <td>aluminium (AlMgSi0.5)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Weight</td> <td>1.5 kg</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Fixing boring</td> <td>Ø 34 mm</td> </tr> </table>	General		Length	1 m	Mounting	at mast tube Ø 40 ... 80 mm	Material	aluminium (AlMgSi0.5)	Weight	1.5 kg	Fixing boring	Ø 34 mm				
General																		
Length	1 m																	
Mounting	at mast tube Ø 40 ... 80 mm																	
Material	aluminium (AlMgSi0.5)																	
Weight	1.5 kg																	
Fixing boring	Ø 34 mm																	
	<p>Northring for First Class Windfahne 509619</p>	<p>The adapter is used for the north alignment of a First Class Wind Direction Sensor.</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td colspan="2">General</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Length</td> <td>75 mm</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Material</td> <td>Alluminum anodized (AlMgSi1)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Weight</td> <td>0.25 kg</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Fixing boring</td> <td>for mast Ø 35 mm for sensor Ø 35 mm</td> </tr> </table>	General		Length	75 mm	Material	Alluminum anodized (AlMgSi1)	Weight	0.25 kg	Fixing boring	for mast Ø 35 mm for sensor Ø 35 mm						
General																		
Length	75 mm																	
Material	Alluminum anodized (AlMgSi1)																	
Weight	0.25 kg																	
Fixing boring	for mast Ø 35 mm for sensor Ø 35 mm																	

WIND

Ultrasonic Anemometer 3D

Part number: 4.383x.2x.xxx

More than 70 different measurement values are available, for ex.:

- Wind velocity in X/Y/Z-direction
- Total wind velocity
- Wind velocity azimuth
- Wind direction azimuth
- Wind velocity elevation
- Wind direction elevation
- Acoustic-virtual temperature
- Standard deviation of the wind velocity in X/Y/Z-direction
- Standard deviation of the total wind velocity
- Standard deviation of the wind velocity azimuth
- Standard deviation of the wind direction azimuth
- Standard deviation of the wind direction elevation
- Standard deviation of the acoustic-virtual temperature
- Statistic functions such as variance, co-variance, turbulence intensity
- Wind velocity X/Y/Z of the gust acc. to WMO
- Wind direction of the gust (elevation) acc. to WMO

The instrument is especially suitable for the use in the fields of

- Meteorology
- Climatology
- Traffic engineering, aviation and navigation
- Indoor flow measurement
- And in alpine field of application

The ultrasonic measurement principle allows, compared to the classic anemometers, an inertia-free measurement of running variable dimensions with highest precision and accuracy. It is especially suitable for the measurement of gust- and peak values.

Specification

Part number: 4.383x.2x.xxx

Wind speed	
Measuring range	0 ... 85 m/s
Resolution	0.1 m/s (standard) 0.01 m/s (user defined)
Accuracy	±(0.1 m/s +1 %) rms (0 ... 35 m/s) ±2 % rms (35 ... 65 m/s) ±3 % rms (65 ... 85 m/s)
Wind direction	
Measuring range	0 ... 360 ° / 540 ° / 720 °
Resolution	1 ° (standard) < 1 ° (user defined)

Accuracy	±1 ° (1 ... 35 m/s) ±2 ° (35 ... 65 m/s) ±4 ° (65 ... 85 m/s)
Virtual temp.	
Measuring range	-50 ... +80 °C
Resolution	0.1 K
Accuracy	±0.5 K
Data output digital	
Interface	RS485 / RS422
Baudrate	1200 Baud ... 921600 Baud
Data values	instant. values, average values, standard deviation
Output range	1 per 10 msec up to 1 per 60 sec
Status signals	heating, Meas section error, Temperature of meas section
Data output analog	
Measured values	WS - Vectors VxVyVz WS - Azimut, WD - Azimut, WS Elevation
Wind speed	0 ... 20 mA; 4 ... 20 mA; 0 ... 10 V; 2 ... 10 V;
Stromausgang	max. 400
Wind direction	0 ... 20 mA; 4 ... 20 mA; 0 ... 10 V; 2 ... 10 V;
Voltage output	min. 4000
Resolution	16 bit
Data input analog (alternative)	
Chanel	3 x 0 ... 10 V
Resolution	16 bit
Operating voltage	
Electronic	8 ... 78 V DC or 12 ... 55 V AC / 2.5 W
Heating	24 V AC/DC, typ 150 W
General	
Bus operation	up to 98 sensors
Electr. connection	8 pol. connector
Mounting	on mast tube 1,5''
Housing	stainless steel (V4A) AiSi316Ti
Protection	IP 67
Dimension	600 mm x 300 mm
Weight	3.4 kg

Versions

As per 4.383x.2x.xxx, but:

Product number 4.3830.20.300

Data output digital	
Baudrate	9600 Baud
Duplex mode	Full duplex
Data telegram	no independent telegram output

Product number 4.3830.20.340

Data output digital	
Baudrate	9600 Baud
Duplex mode	Full duplex
Data telegram	VDT-Telegram (Telegram2)
Output range	10 per 1 sec

Product number 4.3830.21.310

Data output digital	
Baudrate	9600 Baud
Duplex mode	Half duplex
Data telegram	no independent data output
Data output analog	
Type	3 x 4 ... 20 mA

Accessories

Product	Product name	Brief description								
	Connecting cable 50775x	<p>Suitable cable for 4.3820/30/75/80/81</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> length: see versions <p>General</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Cable length</td> <td>see versions</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Cable</td> <td>PUR 4 x 0,75 +2x2x0,14 mm²</td> </tr> </table>	Cable length	see versions	Cable	PUR 4 x 0,75 +2x2x0,14 mm ²				
Cable length	see versions									
Cable	PUR 4 x 0,75 +2x2x0,14 mm ²									
	Northring for Ultrasonic anemometer 508696	<p>The adapter is used for the north alignment of a Ultrasonic anemometer.</p> <p>General</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Length</td> <td>90 mm</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Material</td> <td>Alluminum anodized (AlMgSi1)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Weight</td> <td>0.4 kg</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Fixing boring</td> <td>for mast Ø 50 mm for sensor Ø 50 mm</td> </tr> </table>	Length	90 mm	Material	Alluminum anodized (AlMgSi1)	Weight	0.4 kg	Fixing boring	for mast Ø 50 mm for sensor Ø 50 mm
Length	90 mm									
Material	Alluminum anodized (AlMgSi1)									
Weight	0.4 kg									
Fixing boring	for mast Ø 50 mm for sensor Ø 50 mm									

Meteo-Online
9.1700.98.x01

Meteo-Online is a software for detecting, filing, and displaying data of meteorological measuring instruments. The display of the data is carried out graphically as diagram and/or as text. The user has the possibility to place the display-elements free on the screen, and to save them.

Data display	
Monitor - display	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Values - Diagrams - Tables - Windrose - Time - Date
Compatibility	
Connectable instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - US-Anemometer - Datalogger - Clima Sensor - Weather station WSC11 - Wind display - etc.
System requirements	PC mit <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prozessor > 1 GHz - RAM > 1 GB
Operating system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Windows 2003 SP2 - Windows Server 2008 - Windows 7 - Windows Server 2008 R2 - Windows 7 SP1 - Windows Server 2008 R2 SP1 - Windows 8 - Windows 10

The Solent Research HS-50 has been designed to meet researchers' exacting requirements.

The horizontal symmetrical head allows for more accurate measurement of vertical flows, with minimum interruption from the anemometer geometry.

It can be easily positioned close to the ground or to the crop & tree canopies for accurate measurement of surface turbulence.

Many features are included as standard and it is designed to be simple to use. The head and built in inclinometer allow for easy yet accurate positioning of the instrument on a tower or mast and the separate electronic unit allows simple access to the 6 analogue inputs and PRT 100 input.

The improved head design and rugged stainless steel construction of the HS ensures long term stability and makes it ideal for use in most environments and harsh climates.

*Supplied Accessories - RCOM operating system with a graphical interface (data presentation and storage; flux calculations); electronics unit incorporating Analogue and PRT inputs cable to head; power supply (PCIA); Inclinometer; Transit Case.

Optional Accessories - Analogue Inputs via Power and Communications Interface Unit (PCIA)

Key Features

- 50Hz Data Rate
- Custom Calibrated
- Optional Analogue Outputs
- Speed of Sound and Sonic Temperature Outputs
- Analogue Inputs + PRT Input
- Inclinometer Included
- Carry Case Included

Specification

Wind Speed

Range	0 - 45 m/s
Accuracy	<1% RMS
Resolution	0.01 m/s

Direction

Range	0 - 360°
Accuracy*	<±1° RMS
Resolution	1°

Ultrasonic Measurement

Ultrasonic sampling rate	50Hz
Parameters	UVW, Speed of Sound

Speed of Sound

Range and resolution	300 - 370m/s, 0.01/s
Accuracy	<±0.5%@20°C

Digital Output

Communication	RS422 full duplex, 8 data bits, 1 stop bit, no parity
Baud rates	2400 - 115200
Output rate	Selectable 0.4 - 50Hz

Analogue Inputs

Quantity	6 differential inputs
Sampling rate	100s ⁻¹
Input range/resolution	±5V, 14 bits
Accuracy	<0.1% of FSR

Analogue Outputs (Via supplied PCIA)

Quantity	7(U, V, W, SoS, PRT+2 analogue inputs)
Sampling	±10, ±20, ±30, ±60m/s
Update rate	0.4 to 50Hz
Output range/resolution	±2.5V, 14 bits
Accuracy	<0.25% of FSR

PRT Input (PRT100 not included)

Input resolution	0.01°C
Input accuracy	<0.01°C (from 0°C to 50°C) <0.15°C (from -40°C to +60°C)

Inclinometer

Range/resolution	±20°, 0.01°
Null repeatability	±.15°
Accuracy	±0.3° (from -10° to 10° of inclination)

Power Requirement

Anemometer	9-30VDC <4w (eg. <150mA @ 24VDC or 300mA @ 12VDC)
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Environmental

Operating temperature	-40°C to +60°C
Moisture ingress	IP65
Precipitation	300mm/hr
EMC	EN 50081-1: 1992 Emissions EN 50082-1: 1992 Immunity

General

Suitable for exposure to a marine environment. Instruments housing manufactured in stainless steel.

*Accuracy specification applies for wind speeds <32m/s and for wind incidence <±150° in the horizontal plane and up to ±50° from the horizontal

Typical Applications

- Wind Turbulence Measurement
- Component Wind Velocity UVW
- Wind Profiling
- Maintenance Free
- Robust Construction
- Operates in Precipitation

Dimensions

The HS-50 is part of the Solent range of ultrasonic anemometers.
 The range is in continuous development and therefore specifications may be subject to change without prior notice.

Ultrasonic Wind Sensor uSonic-3 Class A

- High end 3D turbulence probe
- Measurement of 3 wind components and acoustic temperature
- Ideal instrument for eddy-covariance sites
- Embedded 2-axis inclination sensor
- Flow optimized design for boom set-up
- Synchronized analog input channels, 16 Bit
- RS422 / RS485 serial interface
- Sensor head heating
- Measuring range
0 ... 40 m/s , - 40 ... + 70° C
- Easy operation via graphic user interface

Ultrasonic Wind Sensor uSonic-3 Class A

Typical Applications

- Determination of eddy covariance fluxes
- Small scale turbulence research
- Air quality studies
- Research station
- Mast instrumentation on booms

The Ultrasonic Anemometer **uSonic-3 Class A** represents the high precision solution of METEK's ultrasonic sensor family. It has been designed to meet the scientific needs of small scale turbulence measurement or mast instrumentation. With its sensor head optimized for a boom type set-up the flow distortion has been minimized within a wide acceptance angle of 320°.

An embedded 2-axis inclination sensor (option) provides accurate tilt angles of the sensor head. A 6 m cable connects the sensor head to the sensor electronic. Optional up to 6 analog input channels allow synchronized data sampling with 16 bit resolution of fast response sensors of water vapor, carbon dioxide, methan, ozon etc. for eddy covariance installation. The reading of all analog input channels can be individually time shifted to compensate output delays of the external sensors. The sensor delivers raw data (x, y, z, T) and/or online calculated turbulence data sets. Even raw counter readings of each path are available. The system comes with external open end cables of 12 m length for power supply and data transfer.

User interface (GUI)

Graphic output

Sensor head

Sensor electronic

Ambient conditions	- 40 ... + 60 °C, 5 ... 100 %
Average time / number	1 ... 3600 s / 1 ... 65365 samples
Sampling rate	0.1 ... 50 Hz
Measurement ranges	0 ... 40 m/s, - 40 ... + 70 °C
Accuracy (max. dev.) wind speed / wind direction	7.5 cm/s or 1.5 % / 1.5° (@ 5 m/s)
Resolution	0.01 m/s, 0.1°, 0.01 K
Output data set	x, y, z, T / vel, dir, z, T
Averaging method	scalar, vectorial
Output protocols	standard, checksum, NMEA
Data output	async, polling, time synchronized
Turbulence module (option)	online calculation of means, variances, covariances, heat flux, momentum flux, Monin-Obukhov length, etc.
Internal memory	15300 standard / 2600 data sets turbulence calc.
Power supply	9 ... 36 VDC / 3 W (5 W with options)
Sensor head heating (option)	24 VDC / max. 100 W
Analog input (option)	6 x analogue 16 bit, 2 x TTL counter, 2 x PT100
Serial interface	RS422, RS485 (300 ... 115200), ASCII

METEK GmbH, Fritz-Strassmann-Str. 4, 25337 Elmshorn, Germany
 Phone: +49 4121 43590, Fax: +49 4121 4359 20
 E-mail: info@metek.de, Internet: http://www.metek.de

AIR PRESSURE

Baro Transmitter

Part number: 3.1157.10.xxx

- Scalable
 - measuring range
 - Analogue output
- Configurable
 - mean value calculation
 - heating control,
 - energy saving mode,
 - baud rate

The baro transmitter measures the absolute air pressure of the atmosphere at the site. It is designed for application in the field of environmental protection, where high accuracy, quick responding behaviour, long-term stability and reliability are required.

The instrument is suited for in- and outdoor application. A tempered piezo-ceramic sensor for absolute pressure is used, which is characterized by thermal and mechanical stability. The electric connection is done via an 8-pole terminal strip and a special screwed cable gland with smoothing function for air pressure.

The following outputs are available:

- 1 x serial interface
- 1 x frequency output
- 1 x analogue output (U/I)

Specification

Part number: 3.1157.10.xxx

Air pressure	
Measuring range	300 ... 1100 hPa for RS485 output 300 ... 1100 hPa for frequency output for analogue output see models
Accuracy	± 0.25 hPa (with heating) ± 1.00 hPa (without heating)
Long-term stability	± 0.1 hPa / Year
Data output digital	
Output type	RS485 / RS422 und Impulse output
Operating voltage	
Electronic	5 ... 24 V DC (for digital outputs only) otherwise 12 ... 24 V DC
Current consumption	10 mA max. @ 12 V
Heating	12 ... 24 V DC, max. 115 mA @ 12 V
General	
Ambient temp.	-40 ... +65 °C

Electr. connection	terminal strip
Dimension	110 x 82 x 57 mm
Weight	0.15 kg

Versions

As per 3.1157.10.xxx, but:

Product number 3.1157.10.000

Air pressure	
Electr. output	0 ... 5 V -> 800 ... 1060 hPa

Product number 3.1157.10.040

Air pressure	
Electr. output	0 ... 20 mA -> 600 ... 1060 hPa

Product number 3.1157.10.041

Air pressure	
Electr. output	4 ... 20 mA -> 600 ... 1060 hPa

Product number 3.1157.10.061

Air pressure	
Electr. output	0 ... 10 V -> 600 ... 1060 hPa

Product number 3.1157.10.140

Air pressure	
Electr. output	0 ... 20 mA -> 800 ... 1060 hPa

Product number 3.1157.10.141

Air pressure	
Electr. output	4 ... 20 mA -> 800 ... 1060 hPa

Product number 3.1157.10.161

Air pressure	
Electr. output	0 ... 10 V -> 800 ... 1060 hPa

Accessories

Product	Product name	Brief description
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	<p>Traverse for Wind Transmitters Compact 4.3171.3x.000</p>	<p>For mounting the wind transmitter and wind direction transmitter jointly onto a mast.</p>
<p>Material</p>		
<p>Traverse</p>		<p>aluminium (AlMgSi0.5)</p>
<p>Gripping clamb</p>		<p>stainless steel</p>
<p>General</p>		
<p>Sensor distance horizontal</p>		<p>0.8 m</p>
<p>Weight</p>		<p>0.35 kg</p>
<p>Fixing boring</p>		<p>hole Ø 29 mm</p>
	<p>Traverse short for Wind Transmitters Compact 4.3171.4x.000</p>	<p>For mounting one wind transmitter or wind direction transmitter at a mast.</p>
<p>Material</p>		
<p>Traverse</p>		<p>aluminium (AlMgSi0.5)</p>
<p>Gripping clamb</p>		<p>stainless steel</p>
<p>General</p>		
<p>Sensor distance horizontal</p>		<p>0.4 m</p>
<p>Weight</p>		<p>0.3 kg</p>
<p>Fixing boring</p>		<p>hole Ø 29 mm</p>
	<p>Adapter Compact 506345</p>	<p>The adapter serves for mounting a radiation transmitter, baro transmitter or brightness transmitter onto a traverse (4.3171.30.000, 4.3171.40.000) or holder (506 347).</p>
<p>General</p>		
<p>Material</p>		<p>Aluminium, anodized</p>
<p>Dimension</p>		<p>100 x 115 x 65 mm</p>
<p>Weight</p>		<p>0.5 kg</p>

Lufttemperatursensor *standard*

Beschreibung

Robuster und präziser Sensor zur Messung der Temperatur der Umgebungsluft.

Eine Wetterhütte schützt den Sensor vor Regen und Solarstrahlung.

Technische Daten

Sensor

Meßelement.....	Pt 100, nach IEC 751, 1/3 Klasse B
Meßumformer.....	Elektronischer Meßumformer mit Stromausgang
Ausgangssignal.....	-30..+70 °C = 4..20 mA
Genauigkeit.....	10..40 °C ± 0,5 °C
Temperaturkoeffizient.....	± 0,007%/10K für T < 10 °C und T > 40 °C
Einstellzeit.....	90 s (Anstieg auf 90% des Endwerts)
Ausgangslast.....	Max. 100 Ω bei 12 V Versorgungsspannung

Stromversorgung

Versorgungsspannung.....	10..30 VDC
Stromverbrauch.....	Max. 20 mA

Sensorgehäuse

Material.....	Aluminium, hellgrau beschichtet
Schutzart.....	IP 31
Abmessungen.....	ø20 x 150 mm
Schutzkappe.....	Gesinterter Edelstahl

Elektrischer Anschluß

Stecker 7-poliger Rundsteckverbinder, IP 67
 Kabel 2 x 0,5 mm², optional abgeschirmt

Pol- und Adernbelegung

7-poliger Stecker	Adernfarbe	Funktion
3	grün oder weiß	(+) Stromversorgung Temperatur
2	gelb oder braun	Signal Temperatur
Gehäuse	gelb/grün und Kabelschirm	Kabelschirm

Sensor ohne Wetterhütte

Wetterhütte

Typ Passiv belüftete Lamellenwetterhütte
 Material Weißer Kunststoff
 Abmessungen ø120 x 300 mm
 Befestigung Aluminiumwinkel zur Befestigung an einer Wand, Rundbügelschelle aus rostfreiem Edelstahl zur Befestigung an einem Rohr mit einem Außendurchmesser von ø30..50 mm

Umgebungsbedingungen

Umgebungstemperatur -40..+80 °C
 Relative Luftfeuchte 0..100%

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Feuchte-Temperatursensor *standard*

Beschreibung

Robuster und präziser Sensor zur Messung der Temperatur und relativen Feuchte der Umgebungsluft.

Eine Wetterhütte schützt den Sensor vor Regen und Solarstrahlung.

Technische Daten

Sensor

Temperatur

Meßelement.....	Pt 100, nach IEC 751, 1/3 Klasse B
Meßumformer.....	Elektronischer Meßumformer mit Stromausgang
Ausgangssignal	-30..+70 °C = 4..20 mA
Genauigkeit.....	± 0,5 °C
Temperaturkoeffizient.....	± 0,007%/10K für T < 10 °C und T > 40 °C
Einstellzeit.....	90 s (Anstieg auf 90% des Endwerts)
Ausgangslast.....	Max. 100 Ω bei 12 V Versorgungsspannung

Relative Feuchte

Meßelement.....	Kapazitiver Sensor
Meßumformer.....	Elektronischer Meßumformer mit Stromausgang
Ausgangssignal	0..100% rF = 4..20 mA
Genauigkeit.....	5..95% rF ± 2% rF bei 10..40 °C
Temperaturkoeffizient.....	± 0,1%/K für T < 10 °C und T > 40 °C
Einstellzeit.....	90 s (Anstieg auf 90% des Endwerts)
Ausgangslast.....	Max. 100 Ω bei 12 V Versorgungsspannung

Stromversorgung

Versorgungsspannung	10..30 VDC
Stromverbrauch.....	Max. 40 mA

Sensorgehäuse

Material..... Aluminium, hellgrau beschichtet
 Schutzart..... IP 31
 Abmessungen ø20 x 150 mm
 Schutzkappe Gesinterter Edelstahl

Elektrischer Anschluß

Stecker 7-poliger Rundsteckverbinder, IP 67
 Kabel..... 4 x 0,25 mm², optional abgeschirmt

Pol- und Adernbelegung

7-poliger Stecker	Adernfarbe	Funktion
3	weiß	(+) Stromversorgung Feuchte
2	braun	Signal Feuchte
7	grün	(+) Stromversorgung Temperatur
5	gelb	Signal Temperatur
Gehäuse	gelb/grün und Kabelschirm	Kabelschirm

Sensor ohne Wetterhütte

Wetterhütte

Typ Passiv belüftete Lamellenwetterhütte
 Material..... Weißer Kunststoff
 Abmessungen ø120 x 300 mm
 Befestigung..... Aluminiumwinkel zur Befestigung an einer Wand, Rundbügelschelle aus rostfreiem Edelstahl zur Befestigung an einem Rohr mit einem Außendurchmesser von ø30..50 mm

Umgebungsbedingungen

Umgebungstemperatur..... -40..+80 °C
 Relative Luftfeuchte 0..100%

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Ultrasonic Wind Sensor uSonic-3 Scientific

previously USA-1

- High precision 3D sonic anemometer
- Accurate measurement of 3 wind components
- Online calculation of turbulence parameters
- Optimized by wind tunnel calibration
- Robust stainless steel construction
- No moving parts, no maintenance
- Ice protection by efficient sensor heating
- Automatic system monitoring
- Measuring range
0 ... 60 m/s , - 40 ... + 70° C
- Easy operation via graphical user interface

Ultrasonic Wind Sensor uSonic-3 Scientific

previously USA-1

Typical Applications

- Meteorological systems
- Dispersion parameters for pollution modeling
- Air quality studies forecast
- Eddy correlation fluxes
- Wind shear detection
- Wake vortex monitoring
- Meteorological networks
- Research stations
- Industrial sites
- Airports
- Marine and offshore platforms
- Wind energy
- Sport events

The Ultrasonic Anemometer **uSonic-3 Scientific** is a 3D wind and turbulence sensor which has proven reliable operation in all weather types, outstanding flexibility, high rated system performance and user friendly operation in widespread applications. It delivers raw or mean values of wind components x, y, z including acoustic temperature by serial interface RS422 / RS485 or as analogue output.

The **uSonic-3 Scientific** shows a perfect linearity between 0 ... 60 m/s and high resolution in time (max. 30/50 Hz) and data (0.01 m/s, 0.01 K). Absence of inertial masses allows even precise turbulence measurements. Flow distortion effects are compensated by wind tunnel calibration (2D, 3D).

With no moving parts **uSonic-3 Scientific** avoids the shortcomings of mechanical wind sensors: no bearings subject to wear and tear, no shift of calibration parameters, no thresholds, no time delays.

Optional extensions are sensor head heating, analogue data output, analogue data input, separation of sensor head and electronic, online turbulence calculation. Comprehensive online data quality checks and automatic static reports provide for long term system availability.

Ambient conditions	- 40 ... + 60 °C, 5 ... 100 %
Average time / number	1 ... 3600 s / 1 ... 65365 samples
Sampling rate	0.1... 30/50 Hz
Measurement ranges	0 ... 60 m/s, - 40 ... + 70 °C
Accuracy (max. dev.) wind speed / wind direction	0.1 m/s or 2 % / 2° @ 5 m/s
Resolution	0.01 m/s, 0.1°, 0.01 K
Output data set	x, y, z, T / vel, dir, z, T
Averaging method	scalar, vectorial
Output protocols	standard, checksum, NMEA
Data output	async, polling, time synchronized
Turbulence module (option)	online calculation
Internal memory	15300 standard / 2600 data sets turbulence calc.
Power supply	9 ... 36 VDC / 3 W (5 W with options)
Sensor head heating (option)	24 VDC / 55 W / 100 W
Analogue input (option)	2 x PT100, 6 x analog 16 bit, 2 x counter
Analogue output	4 x 0-5V/±5V, 0-10V, ±10V, 0-2,5V, ± 2,5V
Serial interface	RS422, RS485 (300 ... 115200), ASCII

User interface (GUI)

Graphic output

weight: 2,9 kg

PTB110 Barometer for Industrial Use

The Vaisala BAROCAP® Barometer PTB110 offers outstanding long-term stability.

Features/Benefits

- Vaisala BAROCAP® sensor
- Several pressure ranges
- Accuracy ± 0.3 hPa at $+20$ °C
- Long-term stability
- On/off control with external trigger
- Output voltage 0 ... 2.5 or 0 ... 5 VDC
- Current consumption less than 4 mA
- Mountable on a (35 mm wide) DIN rail
- NIST traceable (certificate included)

PTB110

The Vaisala BAROCAP® Barometer PTB110 is designed both for accurate barometric pressure measurements at a room temperature and for general environmental pressure monitoring over a wide temperature range.

Vaisala BAROCAP® Technology

The PTB110 barometer uses the Vaisala BAROCAP® Sensor, a silicon capacitive absolute pressure sensor developed by Vaisala for barometric pressure measurement applications. The sensor combines the outstanding elasticity characteristics and mechanical stability of single-crystal silicon with the proven capacitive detection principle.

Accuracy and Stability

The excellent long-term stability of the barometer minimizes or even removes the need for field adjustment in many applications.

Applications

The PTB110 is suitable for a variety of applications, such as environmental pressure monitoring, data buoys, laser interferometers, and in agriculture and hydrology.

The compact PTB110 is especially ideal for data logger applications as it has low power consumption. Also an external On/Off control is available. This is practical when the supply of electricity is limited.

Technical Data

Operating Range (1 hPa=1mbar)

Pressure ranges	500 ... 1100 hPa
	600 ... 1100 hPa
	800 ... 1100 hPa
	800 ... 1060 hPa
	600 ... 1060 hPa
Temperature range	-40 ... +60 °C (-40 ... +140 °F)
Humidity range	non-condensing

General

Supply voltage	10 ... 30 VDC
Supply voltage control	with TTL level trigger
Supply voltage sensitivity	negligible
Current consumption	less than 4 mA
in shutdown mode	less than 1 µA
Output voltage	0 ... 2.5 VDC
	0 ... 5 VDC
Output frequency	500 ... 1100 Hz
Resolution	0.1 hPa
Load resistance	minimum 10 kohm
Load capacitance	maximum 47 nF
Settling time	1 s to reach full accuracy after power-up
Response time	500 ms to reach full accuracy after a pressure step
Acceleration sensitivity	negligible
Pressure connector	M5 (10-32) internal thread
Pressure fitting	barbed fitting for 1/8"
Minimum pressure limit	0 hPa abs
Maximum pressure limit	2000 hPa abs
Electrical connector	removable connector for 5 wires (AWG 28 ... 16)
Terminals	Pin 1: external triggering
	Pin 2: signal ground
	Pin 3: supply ground
	Pin 4: supply voltage
	Pin 5: signal output
Housing material, plastic cover	ABS/PC blend
Housing classification	IP32
Metal mounting plate	Al
Weight	90 g
Electromagnetic compatibility	Complies with EMC standard EN 61326-1, Electrical equipment for measurement, control and laboratory use - EMC requirements - for use in industrial locations

Accuracy

Linearity*	±0.25 hPa
Hysteresis*	±0.03 hPa
Repeatability*	±0.03 hPa
Pressure calibration uncertainty**	±0.15 hPa
Voltage calibration uncertainty	± 0.7 mV
Frequency calibration uncertainty	± 0.3 Hz
Accuracy at +20 °C***	±0.3 hPa

* Defined as ±2 standard deviation limits of end-point non-linearity, hysteresis error or repeatability error.

** Defined as ±2 standard deviation limits of inaccuracy of the working standard including traceability to NIST.

*** Defined as the root sum of the squares (RSS) of end-point non-linearity, hysteresis error, repeatability error and calibration uncertainty at room temperature when using voltage output.

TOTAL ACCURACY AT

+15 ... +25 °C (+59 ... +77 °F)	±0.3 hPa
0 ... +40 °C (+32 ... +104 °F)	±0.6 hPa
-20 ... +45 °C (-4 ... +113 °F)	±1.0 hPa
-40 ... +60 °C (-40 ... +140 °F)	±1.5 hPa
Long-term stability	±0.1 hPa/year

Dimensions

Dimensions in mm (inches)

BAROCAP® is a registered trademark of Vaisala.

VAISALA

www.vaisala.com

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www.vaisala.com/requestinfo

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HMP155 Humidity and Temperature Probe

HMP155 with an additional temperature probe and optional Stevenson screen installation kit.

The Vaisala HUMICAP® Humidity and Temperature Probe HMP155 provides reliable humidity and temperature measurement. It is designed especially for demanding outdoor applications.

Long-term Stability

The HMP155 has the proven Vaisala HUMICAP®180R sensor that has excellent stability and withstands well harsh environments. The probe structure is solid and the sensor is protected by default with a sintered teflon filter, which gives maximum protection against liquid water, dust, and dirt.

Warmed Probe and High Humidity Environment

Measuring humidity reliably is challenging in environments where humidity is near saturation. Measurements may be corrupted by fog, mist, rain, and heavy dew. A wet probe may not give an accurate measurement in the ambient air.

This is an environment to which Vaisala has designed a patented, warmed probe for reliable measuring. As the sensor head is warmed continuously, the humidity level inside it stays below the ambient level. Thus, it also reduces the risk of condensation forming on the probe.

Fast Measurements

With its fast response time, the additional temperature probe for the HMP155 is ideal for measurement in environments with changing temperatures. The new membrane filter speeds up the RH measurement.

Features/Benefits

- Vaisala HUMICAP®180R sensor - superior long-term stability
- Optional warmed humidity probe and chemical purge
- Plug-and-play
- USB connection for service use
- Fits with DTR13 and DTR503 radiation shields and also for a Stevenson screen
- Weather-proof housing IP66
- Optional, fast temperature probe
- Different output possibilities: voltage, RS-485, resistive Pt100
- Applications: meteorology, aviation and road weather, instrumentation

Long Lifetime

Protecting the sensor from scattered and direct solar radiation, and precipitation will increase its lifetime. Thus, Vaisala recommends installing the HMP155 in one of the following radiation shields: DTR503, DTR13, or a Stevenson screen. For the additional temperature probe, an installation kit is available to be used with DTR502 radiation shield.

Easy Maintenance

The probe can be calibrated using a pc with a USB cable, with the push buttons, or with the MI70 indicator.

Technical Data

Performance

RELATIVE HUMIDITY

Measurement range	0 ... 100 %RH
Accuracy (incl. non-linearity, hysteresis and repeatability) at	
+15 ... +25 °C (+59 ... +77 °F)	±1 %RH (0 ... 90 %RH) ±1.7 %RH (90 ... 100 %RH)
-20 ... +40 °C (-4 ... 104 °F)	±(1.0 + 0.008 x reading) %RH
-40 ... -20 °C (-40 ... -4 °F)	±(1.2 + 0.012 x reading) %RH
+40 ... +60 °C (+104 ... +140 °F)	±(1.2 + 0.012 x reading) %RH
-60 ... -40 °C (-76 ... -40 °F)	±(1.4 + 0.032 x reading) %RH
Factory calibration uncertainty (+20 °C /+68 °F)	±0.6 %RH (0 ... 40 %RH)* ±1.0 %RH (40 ... 97 %RH)*

* Defined as ±2 standard deviation limits. Small variations possible, see also calibration certificate.

Recommended humidity sensor	HUMICAP®180R(C)
Response time at +20 °C in still air with a sintered PTFE filter	
63 %	20 s
90 %	60 s

TEMPERATURE

Measurement range	-80 ... +60 °C (-112 ... +140 °F)
Accuracy with voltage output at	
-80 ... +20 °C	±(0.226 - 0.0028 x temperature) °C
+20 ... +60 °C	±(0.055 + 0.0057 x temperature) °C
passive (resistive) output according to IEC 751 1/3 Class B	±(0.1 + 0.00167 x temperature) °C
RS485 output	
-80 ... +20 °C	±(0.176 - 0.0028 x temperature) °C
+20 ... +60 °C	±(0.07 + 0.0025 x temperature) °C

Accuracy over temperature range (opposite)

Temperature sensor	Pt100 RTD Class F0.1 IEC 60751
Response time with additional temperature probe in 3 m/s air flow	
63 %	<20 s
90 %	<35 s

OTHER VARIABLES

dew point/frost point temperature,
wet bulb temperature, mixing ratio

Dimensions

Dimensions in mm

General

Operating temperature range	-80 ... +60 °C (-112 ... +140 °F)
Storage temperature range	-80 ... +60 °C (-112 ... +140 °F)
Connection	8-pin male M12 connector
Connection cables	3.5, 10, and 30 m
Cable material	PUR
Wire size	AWG26
Service cables	USB connection cable MI70 connection cable
Additional T probe cable length	2 m
Housing material	PC
Housing classification	IP66
Sensor protection	sintered PTFE optional membrane filter
Weight (probe)	86 g
Electromagnetic compatibility: Complies with the EMC standard EN61326-1, Electrical equipment for measurement control and laboratory use - EMC requirement for use in industrial locations	

Inputs and Outputs

Operating voltage	7 ... 28 VDC*
*Note: minimum operating voltage 12 V with 0 ... 5 V output and 16 V with 0 ... 10 V output, probe heating, chemical purge or XHEAT.	
Outputs	
voltage output	0 ... 1 V, 0 ... 5 V, 0 ... 10 V
resistive Pt100 (4-wire connection) RS485	
Average current consumption (+15 VDC, load 100 kOhm)	
0 ... 1 V output	<3 mA
0 ... 10 V output	+0.5 mA
RS485	<4 mA
during chemical purge with warmed probe	max. 110 mA max. 150 mA
Settling time at power-up	
voltage output	2 s
RS485	3 s

VAISALA

www.vaisala.com

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2-wire programmable transmitter

5331A

- RTD, TC, Ohm, or mV input
- Extremely high measurement accuracy
- 1.5 kVAC galvanic isolation
- Programmable sensor error value
- For DIN form B sensor head mounting

Application

- Linearized temperature measurement with Pt100...Pt1000, Ni100...Ni1000, or TC sensor.
- Conversion of linear resistance variation to a standard analog current signal, for instance from valves or Ohmic level sensors.
- Amplification of a bipolar mV signal to a standard 4...20 mA current signal.

Technical characteristics

- Within a few seconds the user can program PR5331A to measure temperatures within all ranges defined by the norms.
- The RTD and resistance inputs have cable compensation for 2-, 3- and 4-wire connection.
- Continuous check of vital stored data for safety reasons.

Mounting / installation

- For DIN form B sensor head or DIN rail mounting with the PR fitting type 8421.

Connections

Order:

Type	Ambient temperature	Galvanic isolation
5331A	-40°C...+85°C : 3	1500 VAC : B

Environmental Conditions

Specifications range.....	-40°C to +85°C
Calibration temperature.....	20...28°C
Relative humidity.....	< 95% RH (non-cond.)
Protection degree (encl./terminal).....	IP68 / IP00

Mechanical specifications

Dimensions.....	Ø 44 x 20.2 mm
Weight approx.....	50 g
Wire size.....	1 x 1.5 mm ² stranded wire
Screw terminal torque.....	0.4 Nm
Vibration.....	IEC 60068-2-6 : 2007
Vibration: 2...25 Hz.....	±1.6 mm
Vibration: 25...100 Hz.....	±4 g

Common specifications**Supply**

Supply voltage.....	7.2...35 VDC
---------------------	--------------

Isolation voltage

Isolation voltage, test / working.....	1.5 kVAC / 50 VAC
--	-------------------

Response time

Response time (programmable).....	1...60 s
Internal consumption.....	25 mW...0.8 W
Voltage drop.....	7.2 VDC
Warm-up time.....	5 min.
Communications interface.....	Loop Link
Signal / noise ratio.....	Min. 60 dB
EEPROM error check.....	< 3.5 s
Accuracy.....	Better than 0.05% of selected range
Signal dynamics, input.....	20 bit
Signal dynamics, output.....	16 bit
Effect of supply voltage change.....	< 0.005% of span / VDC
EMC immunity influence.....	< ±0.5% of span
Extended EMC immunity: NAMUR NE 21, A criterion, burst.....	< ±1% of span

Input specifications**Common input specifications**

Max. offset.....	50% of selected max. value
------------------	----------------------------

RTD input

RTD type.....	Pt100, Ni100, lin. R
Cable resistance per wire (max.).....	5 Ω
Sensor current.....	Nom. 0.2 mA
Effect of sensor cable resistance (3-/4-wire).....	< 0.002 Ω / Ω
Sensor error detection.....	Yes

TC input

Thermocouple type.....	B, E, J, K, L, N, R, S, T, U, W3, W5, LR
Cold junction compensation (CJC).....	< ±1.0°C
Sensor error detection.....	Yes
Sensor error current: When detecting / else.....	Nom. 33 µA / 0 µA

Voltage input

Measurement range.....	-12...800 mV
Min. measurement range (span).....	5 mV

Input resistance.....	10 MΩ
-----------------------	-------

Output specifications**Current output**

Signal range.....	4...20 mA
Min. signal range.....	16 mA
Load resistance.....	≤ (Vsupply - 7.2) / 0.023 [Ω]
Load stability.....	≤ 0.01% of span / 100 Ω
Sensor error indication.....	Programmable 3.5...23 mA
NAMUR NE 43 Upscale/Downscale.....	23 mA / 3.5 mA

Common output specifications

Updating time.....	440 ms
*of span.....	= of the presently selected range

Approvals**General approvals**

EMC.....	EN 61326-1
EAC TR-CU 020/2011.....	EN 61326-1

Ex / I.S.

ATEX 2004/108/EC.....	KEMA 10ATEX0002 X
IECEX.....	DEK 13.0035X
INMETRO.....	DEKRA 13.0001 X
CCOE.....	P337392/1

Marine approval

DNV Marine.....	Stand. f. Certific. No. 2.4
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WINDCUBE™

L I D A R R E M O T E S E N S O R

LEOSPHERE
Lidar Environmental Observations

Global Partners in Lidar Wind Technologies

200m wind profile

10 programmable measurement heights

1-second sampling rate

Portable, flexible, easy to use

Constant accuracy at all heights

Complements met mast data

Ready to use data (automatic data filter)

Built for all weather conditions

Customer Windcubes in use around the World

Power curve verification by Vestas

Varied terrain study by Acciona

Loading Windcube into helicopter

Site assessment by Alpha Wind

Return on Innovation

The profitability of a wind farm project depends on two major challenges: reducing data uncertainty and reducing project risks.

Reducing data uncertainty for wind resources is critical. The wind energy industry is looking for innovative, cost effective ways to obtain site assessments and due diligences—as quickly as possible.

- So why extrapolate the wind data at 200m when you can measure it directly?
- Why extrapolate the data over the whole surface of the site when you can measure directly at various locations?

An easily deployable lidar wind profiler reduces risk by extending measurement data beyond a mast and accelerates the assessment process with simple procedures.

“Measure 200 meter data directly”

The Windcube™ lidar remote sensor provides 200m vertical wind profiles on various possible locations, mapping wind speed and direction, turbulence, and wind shear.

**Customer Service
& Support Worldwide**

No Matter Where
Your Windsite Is

- 200m wind profile
- 10 programmable measurement heights
- 1-second sampling rate
- Portable, flexible, easy to use
- Constant accuracy at all heights
- Complements met mast data
- Ready to use data (automatic data filter)
- Built for all weather conditions

“Raise a tower of light”

The Windcube™ brings an innovative tool to the wind industry by offering an independently tested, compact, secure and easy to set up lidar remote sensor with unmatched performance, and ideally designed for wind measuring activities.

Operational Easy to deploy, operate, and redeploy. With minimum maintenance required, the Windcube™ acts like any other meteorological sensor.

Cost and time effective Quick to deploy with no construction permits required. Minimum installation time and labor. Ideal for offshore projects.

Reduce risk With actual wind measurements up to 200m, reduce the uncertainty from vertical and horizontal extrapolation of site assessment models. In complex sites, get real turbulence and wind shear measurements.

Worldwide Services Leosphere and NRG Systems provide the end user support and services through their global network.

Innovation The Windcube™ lidar remote sensor will provide you with a powerful, flexible, mobile sensor for 200m performance that complements met masts and cup anemometers.

Applications: Site Assessment and Site Performance

The typical size of wind turbines continues to grow and wind farm projects become more and more difficult to reliably assess. However, whether large and expansive, on-shore or off-shore, wind farm developments require new and innovative ways of measuring wind.

“Measuring the wind at 200m is getting critical”

Understanding the wind flow over very large areas, in forest or mountainous sites, may be very difficult. Obstacles that affect the wind resource such as trees or cliffs dramatically modify the homogeneity and distribution of the wind. Additional wind data at higher heights and at multiple locations is critical to reliably predict the wind farm potential.

Get a 200 meter wind profile with data at 20 meter intervals and 1-second sample rate. Features that allow the use of the Windcube lidar remote sensor for various applications.

Wind Consultants and Developers

- Site prospecting (pre-evaluation of wind potential before investing in long-term measurement campaign)
- Site assessment
- Verification of vertical profile extrapolation (WASP)
- Optimizing the P numbers
- Micro-siting
- Power curve verification
- Site repowering

Manufacturers and Turbine Designers

- Impact of vertical profile and turbulence on turbine performance
- Power curve verification

The Windcube is being used in over 18 countries by developers, consultants, turbine manufacturers, and research institutes.

Performance Specifications

Specifications	
Range min - max	40 to 200m
Accumulation time	0.5s
Data output frequency	1 Hz
Probe depth	20m
Number of measurement heights	10
Scanning cone angle	Dual 15° or 30°
Speed accuracy	0,2 m/s
Speed range	0 to +60 m/s
Direction accuracy**	1.5°

Parameters	
Output data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1s/10min horizontal & vertical wind speed, min & max, direction - Signal-to-Noise Ratio - Horizontal & vertical wind speed standard deviation

Maximum Range (M) Vs Visibility (Km) Simulations For 30m Range Resolution

Independent Met Mast Correlation: Industry Proven in 2 Years of Intensive Field Testing

Horizontal Wind Speed Component as Measured by Windcube Against Cup Anemometer Readings at 98.7m (Source: DWG)

10min Average Lidar Horizontal Wind Speed Compared with Risø Cup Anemometer at 116m (Source: Risø)

Other independent validation reports are available upon request

Technical Specifications

Electrical	
Power supply	24V DC or 100/240V AC 50-60 Hz
Power consumption	111W to 375W
Environmental	
Temperature range	-30°C to +40°C (with winter package)
Operating humidity	IP65
Rain protection	Wiper
Compactness	Portable
Optics & Electronics	
Laser	Class 1 - 1.54 μm
Eye safety	IEC 60825-1
Dimensions	
Size	800x550x550 mm
Weight	60 kg
Data	
Data format	ASCII / binary
Data transfer	GSM / GPRS / LAN / TCP-IP

“Deploy your Windcube™ anywhere you need it... plug it in and start measuring”

200m Wind Profile

Automatic Data Filtering

Protection

We have been carrying out several environmental long-term tests on the Windcube™ system. The Windcube is enclosed in an IP65 waterproof and dustproof housing, which protects the system from harsh weather conditions. The system is also equipped with window de-icing and an automatic wiper system. The Windcube accuracy has been proven in rain, snow, and cold climates.

Winter Package

An environmental condition module and insulated cover allow the system to operate in arctic conditions down to -30°C.

Software

Standard WINDSOFT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Instrument control - Data acquisition - Data storage - Data treatment - Manual data transfer (TCP/IP)
Optional Expert	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - raw data (spectra data) - signal to noise ratio - calibration data
Optional Windcube Anywhere	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Automatic remote data transfer (GSM/GPRS) - Sendmail: email data sending - System remote control - Remote alarm by sms or email
GPS tracking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GPS data

Windcube™ Lidar Wind Technologies

Pulsed laser benefits: simultaneous and constant probed depth

Thanks to its pulsed laser source, the resolution and accuracy of the Windcube™ remain the same at any height. The Windcube optics do not need to focus at each height. The other advantage of a pulsed source is simultaneous measurements at any height. The Windcube can retrieve up to 10 measurement heights every second.

“10 programmable measurement heights”

Complex terrain measurements

The Windcube lidar system has been used for complex terrain assessment studies with very good results. Leosphere and NRG Systems continue to work with key industry experts to increase the understanding of Windcube measurements in complex terrain. State-of-the-art scientific papers provide additional analysis.

For additional information: www.whitepapers.lidarwindtechnologies.com.

“Automatic data filter”

With the same approach of “ready to use data,” Leosphere and NRG Systems are testing a software module that could avoid any ambiguity in the output data of the Windcube. This software feature is being tested in relative and very complex sites.

The technological flexibility of the Windcube lidar allows Leosphere and NRG Systems to continue various studies on this topic, with the help of major wind consultants and research institutes.

More information on lidar complex terrain measurements is available upon request at info@leosphere.fr.

Technology

Pulsed Laser Optical Vision

Lidar principle

The Windcube™ is an active remote sensor based on laser detection and ranging technique. The heterodyne lidar principle relies on the measurement of the Doppler shift of laser radiation backscattered by the particles in the air (dust, water droplets from clouds and fog, pollution aerosols, salt crystals, biomass burning aerosols...).

Technological breakthrough

Leosphere holds a complete lidar product range (aerosol, wind and humidity lidar) and key expertises in lidar systems development and industrialization. Developed in cooperation with the French Aerospace agency (ONERA), the Windcube™ is the result of 20 years of research and development. Its inventors have overcome major technological challenges to give birth to the new generation of wind lidar system.

Sample Volume Doppler Lidar Retrieval

Key Benefits

- 200m wind profile
- 10 programmable measurement heights
- 1-second sampling rate
- Portable, flexible, easy to use
- Constant accuracy at all heights
- Complements met mast data
- Ready to use data (automatic data filter)
- Built for all weather conditions

Lidar Industrial Grade Quality

Quality management and testing

The quality and performance reproducibility of Windcube products are ensured by the following steps:

- Regular quality and performance tests during various steps of the manufacturing process (components, optical chain, SNR)
- Internal commissioning: Several weeks of continuous measurements and data comparison against a reference Windcube lidar system. The reference Windcube system has been tested by Risø and WindGuard.

Lean manufacturing

Leosphere, in working with NRG Systems, has implemented lean manufacturing processes. This allows optimization of production according to a client's demand and delivery time. This process has improved our responsiveness by 30%.

For Industrial Sales and Consultation Contact:

Europe

LEOSPHERE
Bâtiment 503 - Centre Scientifique d'Orsay
Plateau du Moulon
91400 Orsay, France
info@leosphere.fr

Americas

NRG Systems, Inc.
110 Riggs Road, Hinesburg, VT 05461 USA
info@nrgsystems.com

Asia | Africa

For contacting our representatives in Asia:
www.lidarwindtechnologies.com/distribution
info@lidarwindtechnologies.com

Oceania

NRG Systems, Inc.
110 Riggs Road, Hinesburg, VT 05461 USA
info@nrgsystems.com

Service and Support

The Windcube™ is much more than a simple sensor. We provide our customers with additional services and options that make it even easier to use your system.

Worldwide Service and Support

The products and services are developed, marketed, and offered globally through the partnership of Leosphere and NRG Systems. The user's benefit is global support and service through the Leosphere and NRG Systems partnership.

Remote Power Supply

For remote site operation, several solutions for powering the Windcube are available. For more information please contact us.

Warranty

The Windcube is provided with a 1-year warranty as standard.

Warranty extension

Leosphere and NRG Systems offer several warranty extension options for users that need to complete a long-term project.

1 year full warranty

Diagnostics within 48 Hours

**Customer Service
& Support Worldwide**

No Matter Where
Your Windsite Is

LEOSPHERE
Lidar Environmental Observations

Global Partners in Lidar Wind Technologies

www.lidarwindtechnologies.com

WINDCUBE[®] v2

L I D A R R E M O T E S E N S O R

LEOSPHERE
Lidar Environmental Observations

Global Partners in Lidar Wind Technologies

WINDCUBE® v2 Key benefits

- Ultra portable 200m wind profiler (45 kg)
10 min installation
- Class 1 anemometer
matched accuracy
- Ideal for complex terrain using
CFD software engine
- Unmatched reliability & data availability
- Backed by the industry leaders

WINDCUBE®v2 : Reduce Uncertainty and Increase Profitability

The profitability of a wind farm project depends on two major challenges: reducing data uncertainty and reducing project risks. Uncertainties are related to both turbine response and wind resource estimation.

Project uncertainties vary from site to site and are highly dependent on project size and site complexity. Acceptable best practice for the resource assessment community has been the use of a lidar remote sensor in combination with met masts. The practice of utilizing fixed met masts for an extended measurement period in conjunction with a moving lidar system, for shorter measurement periods, provides the best solution for reducing uncertainty. The original Windcube is operating worldwide for 4 years in more than 20 countries.

200m wind profile

The NEW ultra portable WINDCUBE®v2 lidar remote sensor provides 200m vertical wind profiles on various terrain types providing wind speed, direction, and wind shear. A successful wind measurement campaign that includes the WINDCUBE®v2 lidar remote sensor allows for the reduction of several sources of uncertainty in wind resource estimation, leading to higher return on your investment. On a typical 50MW wind farm project this reduction in uncertainty can equate to 1.5M€ in equity investment savings and a significant increase in the rate of return.* The WINDCUBE®v2 lidar remote sensor is a quantifiably valuable asset for developers, consultants, wind farm owners and operators.

[Return on Investment of a Lidar System for Wind Resource Assessment, poster EWEC2010](#)

WINDCUBE®v2 Applications

Project siting on land & offshore: Simple installation – no permitting required. Excellent for pre-site evaluation.

Power Performance: From turbine commissioning to permanent monitoring of your farms power deliverables.

Unmatched Turbulence Measurements: Turbulence Intensity, Turbulent Kinetic energy, inflow angle.

Technical Data

Specifications

MEASUREMENTS

Range	40m to 200m
Data sampling rate	1s
Number of programmable heights	10
Speed accuracy	0.1m/s
Speed range	0 to +60m/s
Direction accuracy	2°

ELECTRICAL

Power supply	18-32V DC / 100 to 230 VAC 50-60 Hz
Power consumption	45W

ENVIRONMENTAL

Temperature range	-30°C to +45°C / -22 °F to 108°F
Operating humidity	0 ... 100 %RH (non condensing)
Housing classification	IP67
Shocks & vibration	ISTA / FEDEX 6A
Safety	Class 1M IEC/EN 60825-1
Compliance	CE

TRANSPORTATION

Size	System : 543 x 552 x 540mm Transport case : 685x745x685mm
Weight	System : 45 kg Transport case : 21 kg

SOFTWARE/DATA

Data format	ASCII
Data storage	SSD and compact flash (backup storage)
Data transfer	LAN/USB
Standard WINDSOFT™ Software	Configuration & control real time display diagnostic
Output data	1s/10min Horizontal & vertical wind speed min & max, direction, SNR Quality factor (data availability) GPS coordinates

Lidar Technology Overview

The WINDCUBE® v2 is an active remote sensor based on Light Detection And Ranging technique. Wind lidar relies on the measurement of Doppler shifted laser light backscattered by particles in the atmosphere (dust, aerosols). Lidar is the only remote sensor technology to measure the absolute speed of the wind, making it the best choice to meet the industry's high accuracy requirements.

Optional Features and Services

WINDCUBE® POWER PACK

Based on fuel cells technology, the WINDCUBE® power pack is the ultimate solution for remote locations. Ultra portable, green and affordable, this stand alone power supply is available worldwide (950x690x480mm -1 box / 35 kg).

WINDCUBE® CFD software engine

Remote sensors and traditional anemometry have always shown discrepancies in complex terrain due to their different measurement principles. Developed in partnership with CFD modeling companies (Meteodyn, Windsim), the unique software engine provides accurate data results in any topography. Proven accuracy <2%.

WINDCUBE® ANYWHERE SAT/3G

The built-in modem and universal SIM card provide a secured web based interface from any location. The WINDCUBE® Anywhere option features:

- Remote access to real time data
- System health monitoring
- Data management

GPS GEOFENCING SECURITY

The optional GPS security provides reliable, affordable, peace of mind. Over 100 units have been operating worldwide.

WINDCUBE® v2 OFFSHORE

We supply specific solutions for reliable offshore WINDCUBE®v2 operation featuring an IP67 reinforced enclosure:

- Satellite data access
- Marine protective coating
- Dedicated offshore maintenance services

QUALITY & DELIVERY

Our optimized lean manufacturing processes allow us to deliver your WINDCUBE® v2 product with minimal lead time in a repeated quality.

WARRANTY & MAINTENANCE CONTRACTS

Both Leosphere and NRG Systems offer several options for warranty extensions and service contracts that provide fixed cost-of-ownership over the life of your project.

Diagnostic support within 48 hours Guaranteed uninterrupted operation

Customer Service & Support Worldwide

No Matter Where Your Wind site Is

www.lidarwindtechnologies.com

info@lidarwindtechnologies.com

ZephIR Lidar

our vision: a wind lidar on every commercial wind project
and integrated into every large wind turbine

we are wind lidar

For over ten years ZephIR Lidar has been providing high-resolution wind measurements onshore, offshore - on both fixed and floating platforms - and mounted on wind turbines for wind energy and meteorological applications globally.

All with the original wind lidar product family
ZephIR 300 and ZephIR DM.

continuous wave wind lidar

At the heart of ZephIR 300 and ZephIR DM continuous wave technology lives one of the most robust and sensitive lasers available.

And that's important because it let's us give you a 3 year service period onshore helping to reduce your operational costs, a wind data point every 20 milliseconds to 'freeze' any motion encountered when mounted on turbines or on floating buoys, full rotor scanning for turbine upwind characteristics expected in forthcoming IEC guidelines, and 50Hz data capture for true 1 second measurements.

Not all lidars are the same, ours is easy to remember though -

**3 years warranty, DNV GL Stage 3,
3% lower energy uncertainty than an IEC onshore met mast
at an equivalent cost over 3 years
and has 3 legs.**

ZephIR 300

The industry's most validated wind lidar¹ for ground-based, 10 metre to 200+ metre wind measurements ideal for site resource assessment, power curve measurements and bankable Annual Energy Prediction (AEP) campaigns at the lowest cost of lidar ownership available and a 3 year ZephIR Care warranty as standard onshore with no requirement for annual servicing or calibration.

¹Over 200 performance validations against a consistent, IEC compliant met mast site

ZephIR DM

The unique Dual-Mode wind lidar for turbine-mounted, high resolution, full rotor wind measurements upwind of a wind turbine from 10 metres to 300+ metres to benchmark turbine performance, identify opportunities for increased production and inform O&M strategies. All with the added functionality of ground-based deployments from the same core product.

absolute accuracy

ZephIR 300 has been deployed in a world first 'absolute accuracy' test in LM Windpower's wind tunnel, Denmark.

ZephIR 300 successfully measured wind speeds

with an averaged difference of just 0.4%

for a sustained period of time and across all measured speeds.

from the most* validated remote sensor

ZephIR 300 has been successfully validated in more than 200 Performance Verifications *at a consistent IEC 61400-12-1 Compliant Site, approved for use by technical and engineering services providers DNV GL, and Natural Power.

Data availability is, on average, 97% through all heights measured and up to 200 metres from ground level.

commercial experience

Operational site measurements

Extreme snow conditions

ZephIR + Short-mast project financing

Proven accuracy onshore

Wind farm trouble-shooting

Packaged power and ZephIR

Autonomous operation

Satellite communications pack

Desert conditions and extreme high temperatures

Complex terrain finance-grade measurements

specification

DATA HEADING	UNIT	EXPLANATION
Reference	-	Numerical reference of each record
Time and date	-	In text format, to the nearest second
Timestamp	Seconds	Time and date of the reading as numerical value in seconds
Info. flags	-	Operational mode information
Status flags	-	Internal ZephIR status
Battery	Volts	Internal battery voltage
Generator	Volts	External supply voltage, if present
Upper temp / lower temp	Degrees Celsius	Pod temperature
Pod humidity	Percent	Internal ZephIR humidity
GPS	Decimal Degrees	GPS location (lat and long)
ZephIR bearing	Degrees	Direction of the ZephIR wrt True North
Tilt	Degrees	Pitch and roll away from vertical
Air Temp.	Degrees Celsius	Ambient temperature
Pressure	Millibar / Hectopascals	Ambient pressure
Humidity	Percent	Ambient humidity
Met station wind speed	Metres per second	Horizontal wind speed measured by the Met station
Met station direction	Degrees	Wind direction measurement by the Met station
Raining	-	Rain sensor detects rain
Horizontal wind speed	Metres per second	Horizontal wind speed measured by ZephIR
Vertical wind speed	Metres per second	Vertical wind speed measured by ZephIR
Horizontal min / max	Metres per second	Minimum / maximum horizontal wind speeds measured by ZephIR
TI	-	Turbulence Intensity

PERFORMANCE	ZephIR 300
Range (min.)	10 metres
Range (max.)	200 metres
Probe length @ 10 m	± 0.07 metres
Probe length @ 100 m	± 7.70 metres
Heights measured	10 (user-configurable)
Sampling rate	50Hz
Averaging period	user configurable (1 second as standard)
Scanning cone angle	30° (other angles available)
Speed accuracy variation*	< 0.1 m/s
Speed range	< 1 m/s to 70 m/s
Direction accuracy variation*	< 0.5°

OPERATIONS	ZephIR 300
Temp range (min.)	-40°C
Temp range (max.)	+50°C
Power consumption	69 Watts**
Power input	12 V
Weight (excluding flight casing)	55 kg
Service interval	36 months

DATA	ZephIR 300
10 minute averaging	90Kb / day
1 second data	3MB / day
On board storage	36 months
Data transfer	LAN; MODBUS; WiFi; Global SIM; Sat Comms
Timestamp / Location	GPS

SAFETY	ZephIR 300
Laser classification	Class 1
Eye safety standard	IEC 60825-1
IP Rating	IP67
Compliance	Full CE accreditation

* As measured against a calibrated moving target. ** In off-grid, DC power situations, excluding any convertor losses and in standard climates. Always refer to manufacturers guidelines on power before specifying 3rd party power solutions. Alternatively use the ZephIR Power support package.

- MARINE METEOROLOGICAL STATION** providing temperature, pressure and humidity measurements, designed to operate in harsh marine environments and includes a GPS device for data timestamp & location facilitating synchronisation with other devices
- AUTOMOTIVE MOISTURE SENSOR** for activating wiper arm, flagging periods of precipitation and designed to operate in exhaustive automotive applications
- MARINE WIPER SYSTEM** with silicone wiper blade for extended operation, keeping window surface clear of moisture and debris, designed to operate in the harshest of environments fed by industrial specification screen wash capable of operation in sub-zero temperatures
- INSULATED ENCLOSURE** manufactured in twin-skin Polyethylene, operating across all temperature ranges (-40°C to +50°C) and with IP seals across all surfaces and connector panels
- 3 X CARBON FIBRE LEGS** resistant to horizontal wind loading while keeping overall weight minimised, and providing a proven tripod levelling system
- MARINE GRADE ROPE** at three locations around waist of product for ease of lifting across uneven terrain
- QUICK RELEASE HANDLES** for simple levelling adjustments and designed for gloved operation
- WIDE SPREAD FEET** for stable footing in all terrains and all ground surfaces with security bolt through apertures

3 years warranty and support, 3 year service interval
and 3 years courtesy lidar cover.

ZephIR Care answers the need for truly autonomous provision of wind data onshore and provides you with the ability to operate ZephIR 300 in the field for unbroken measurement campaigns of 3 years particularly suitable in applications where the sensor must remain in place long-term such as during an Annual Energy Prediction. In these campaigns the economic viability of recovering a sensor demands the highest levels of reliability and support, now delivered by ZephIR Lidar.

3 years warranty

**3 years dedicated technical support engineer
via telephone and to perform remote diagnostics**

An IEC compliant met mast validation

Optional daily monitoring

Choice of data delivery (email, FTP, web interface, real-time)

**A 'courtesy' ZephIR 300 in any event where an infield issue cannot be
quickly resolved remotely**

How? This support offering is as unique as the continuous wave laser technology inside ZephIR, and continuous wave = continuous operation.

zephirlidar.com
sales@zephirlidar.com

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Wind can go anywhere. So can the AQ500.

Finding the right wind is hardly a static task. By pure definition it's a moving element that knows no boundaries. So why use traditional met masts when you can get all your bankable data more efficiently with the speed of sound?

 AQSystem
Remote sensing technique

AQ500 windfinder

No matter where the wind goes, our mobile and self-sufficient Sodar system AQ500 Windfinder can go there too. It measures wind conditions up to a height of 200 metres with the help of sound waves.

Sodar technology operates in a similar fashion to sonic radar, detecting even the slightest wind well above the highest blade of any hub. So you can be sure to get all the bankable data needed without any uncertainty.

One switch start-up

The AQ500 is a simple solution that you can set-up with no previous experience after having attended the AQSystem technical training. All you have to do is position it and activate the power switch. The system is already pre-calibrated at our factory.

Instant wind data

Time is a key factor in every wind project. The AQ500 has proven to be the most efficient method for measuring wind conditions, eliminating the need for permits, subcontractors or construction.

Instead you can just make sure that the rest of the project run just as smoothly as the site assessment.

With the AQ500 you can start your site assessment at least 6 months earlier than when using the more traditional met mast. This will not only get your turbines spinning faster but will also turn your investment into to a more profitable venture.

Easy deployment

The AQ500 is lightweight and small enough to be transported by car. When an installation is challenged by some more diverse terrain, the four lifting hooks on top of the trailer will allow a helicopter to transport the AQ500 to even the most remote of locations.

Completely self-sufficient

As the AQ500 must be able to work anywhere, its energy requirements are low. The system only needs a solar panel to recharge the powerful battery bank. During the winter months when there is little sunshine the small power generator acts as a back-up.

The AQ500

Met mast

Unique Sodar design

The measuring antennas are well protected in the AQ500 Sodar, allowing accurate results even in the most adverse weather conditions. With no moving parts, unlike the anemometer on a met mast, the AQ500 will not freeze or shut down.

200 metres measuring range

Height is the key element for measuring wind because hubs today often rise well over 100 metres above ground level. Traditional met masts just can't keep up any longer – especially if you consider that more than 50 percent of power is generated at the highest rotor blade.

So to not leave anything to chance, the AQ500 measures up to 200 metres with a 5-metre resolution. This registers any wind movement beyond the highest blade of any hub today or in the foreseeable future, with an accuracy of 0.1 m/s.

All terrain compatibility

The AQ500 can be used in really complex terrain with the help of triangulation. With a combination of systems you can now measure a “common volume” in a single spot – even if an area has complex height variations.

Certified stand-alone solution

AQSystem started working with Sodar technology in the 1960's and have delivered several hundred AQ500 Windfinders since its release in 2007. Several independent test institutes have evaluated the system and approved it as a certified stand-alone solution.

Technical specifications

Environment

Temperature range	-40 °C to + 60 °C
Humidity range	10 to 100 % RH

AQ500 Windfinder trailer

Height	2,2 meter
Width	1,4 meter
Length	3,0 meter
Weight	1180 kg
Fuel tank	200 litre

Data

Data transfer	GSM / GPRS
Data format	ASCII

AQ500 antenna

Height	1,2 meter
Width Ø	1,0 meter
Weight	70 kg

Electrical

Power supply	Solar / Generator / 230 VAC / 120 VAC
Power consumption	30 – 50 W
Pulse power (max)	300 W
Acoustic power (max)	17 W

Support & Service

As the AQ500 Windfinder can go anywhere we must be able to do the same. At AQSystem we therefore have a well-established support and service organisation.

We can for example offer you the following:

- 1-year factory warranty on all AQ500 parts.
- Individual service contract according to your need.
- Hot line support for hardware or software issues.
- On-site service, diagnostics and repair.
- Spare parts for a period of seven years.

The AQ500

AQSystem have been working with sonic radar since the 1960's and the AQ500 Windfinder is the most popular Sodar solution of its size in the market today. Since its release in 2007 several hundred units are being used everyday all around the world.

These are some examples of our clients, please find out more about them and how they use the AQ500 by visiting www.aqs.se/case-studies

Features

- High height data — to 200 meters
- No permitting required
- Extremely low power consumption (7 watts)
- Data access and monitoring via secure web portal
- Ease of deployment — installed and collecting data within 2 hours
- > 99.9 % operational uptime based on more than 800 commercial systems deployed worldwide since April 2008

Triton[®] Wind Profiler is a durable, robust, and independent sonic detection and ranging (SODAR) device used for profiling wind regimes at a given location.

A Resource Assessment System For Today's Wind Turbines

Vaisala Triton Wind Profiler is an advanced SODAR that provides wind data well above the rotor tip-height of today's large wind turbines. Triton captures extensive data on anomalous wind events such as speed and direction shear and turbulence that directly affect wind turbines' power output — and that could affect a wind farm's performance.

Low Power Consumption

Triton requires only 7 W of power for continuous operation. Technology innovations like low-power amplifier chips and the Blackfin ARM enable Triton to be powered by two solar panels and to run continuously without being attended.

High Height Data

Triton captures wind data at heights up to 200 meters, reducing uncertainty inherent in the use of extrapolated data from meteorological towers. At

120 meters, high quality filtered data captured by Triton normally exceeds 90 % (averaged over a 12-month period). Triton's performance has been validated by studies correlating its measurements with anemometers at a number of sites.

Monitoring and Data Access Via Secure Web Portal

Download and analyze your wind data at any time, from any location via the Internet. Access ten-minute averages in real-time over a secure web server, and easily read and understand the data. In addition, our support team can monitor your Triton's operations daily.

Easy to Deploy and Relocate

The low-profile Triton can be deployed and transmitting data within a few hours. With no moving parts, solid-state electronics, and a tough, lightweight low-density polyethylene (LDPE) enclosure, Triton is well equipped for redeployments in the toughest environments, in all climates.

Use Tritons for Every Stage of Your Wind Project:

- Greenfield prospecting
- Micrositing and turbine suitability
- Wind shear validation
- Hub height wind speed validation
- Ramp event forecasting
- Reducing spatial uncertainty
- Power curve testing and nacelle anemometer correlation

Technical Data

Data Capture

Maximum height	200 m (656 ft)
Wind data capture heights	40, 50, 60, 80, 100, 120, 140, 160, 180, and 200 m (131, 164, 196, 262, 328, 393, 459, 524, 590, and 656 ft)
Wind speed	0 ... 40 m/s (0 ... 90 mph)
SD memory card socket	2 GB SD card records a minimum of 2 years of 10 min data
Data upload rate	Every 10 minutes, via satellite/cell link ¹⁾ Automatic data buffering and backfilling protocol.
Data recovery rate (unfiltered)	> 98 % (at all heights)
Filtered data correlation	Within 2 % of anemometers
Nominal Filtered Data Recovery Rate (With > 90 % Quality Factor) ²⁾	
At 100 m (328 ft)	Approx. 90 ... 95 % or higher
At 120 m (393 ft)	Approx. 88 ... 92 % or higher
At 140 m (459 ft)	Approx. 85 ... 90 % or higher

¹⁾ Check with Vaisala for availability of satellite and cell modems for each region

²⁾ Filtered data recovery rate represents the percentage of Triton data with a Quality Factor > 90 % averaged over a 12-month period to account for seasonal and diurnal effects. Application of a minimum QF of 90 % removes low quality data associated with atmospheric stability, atmospheric absorption, and precipitation events. The Triton's Filtered Data Recovery Rate is equivalent to "directionally filtered data" from met tower-mounted anemometers.

Power Supply

Average power consumption	7 W
Solar panels	2 panels, each rated at 85 W
Internal batteries	Leak-proof AGM marine batteries, rated 12 V, 92 Ah
Battery capacity	Internal shipping-safe mounting system holds up to 4 batteries for 20 days of operation without charging. (See note under Snow Removal Package/Battery Capacity)

Installation

Footprint	2 × 3 m (6 ft × 9 ft) with solar panels fitted
Orientation	Dual-axis accelerometer for automatic correction for out-of-level Site location determined by GPS
Leveling of base	Within 3° of level in x and y axis

Operation

Ambient temperature	-40 ... +65 °C (-40° ... +150 °F)
Frequency of sound beams	4500 Hz (nominal) with automatic temperature correction
Number of sound beams	3
Data sampling rate	Approx. 100 'chirps' per sound beam per 10-minute period
Duration of sound 'chirp'	60 ... 100 ms
Sound level at ear level (intermittent sound source)	0 m: 87 dBa 50 m (164 ft): 63 dBa

Transportation

Dimensions	2 × 2 × 2 m (6 ft × 6 ft × 6 ft) 1.2 m (3 ft 11 in) wide base fits in pick-up truck bed or trailer
Weight	350 ... 450 kg (750 ... 1000 lb) depending on configuration
Integrated shipping	Triton and all accessories ship as one unit

Dimensions in cm (inches), rounded to the nearest unit. Solar panels and mounting hardware not shown.

Optional Snow Removal Package

Energy source	LPG (propane)
Storage capacity (to be provided by the customer)	Triton enclosure has nesting locations for (1) 18 kg (40 lb) and (1) 14 kg (30 lb) LPG bottles with a combined capacity of 32 kg (70 lb)
Run time	Up to 200 h of snow melting with 32 kg (70 lb) internal propane supply
Heater control	Intelligent system with satellite control capacity
Battery capacity	For heater-equipped Tritons, frequent heater activations will reduce the time of battery operation without a charging event

Configurations

Standard Triton configuration	2 batteries 2 solar panels Globalstar modem and antenna 4 screw-in ground anchor
Snow Removal Package	Above, plus complete snow-melting heater system

VAISALA

www.vaisala.com

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WINDCUBE⁺

100S/200S/400S

3D Wind Doppler Lidar

SITE ASSESSMENT

POWER CURVE

WAKE MEASUREMENT

FORECASTING

Leosphere
THE ATMOSPHERE IS YOURS

Scanning wind doppler Lidars systems offer a fully integrated operational capacity to improve wind measurement at any stage of a wind farm project, from prospecting to operation. WINDCUBE 100S / 200S / 400S perform a full 3D mapping of the atmosphere to provide enhanced measurements of wind speed and direction.

Wind farm challenges

The development of the wind industry creates new challenges, such as the need to better measure wind resources at either one location or on a larger scale area.

The increasing size of the wind farms requires a mapping of wind resources, offering a better understanding of turbine-to-turbine or farm-to-farm wake effect. Accurate forecasting is the overall goal, particularly as wind farms increase in size.

Scanning wind doppler Lidars such as WINDCUBE 100S / 200S / 400S are the equipment of choice to address these challenges.

Scanning Lidars bring value to the wind energy market: Applications

Site assessment: to determinate the location of a future wind farm by predefining the best location for Lidar for the further site assessment, on-shore site assessment (horizontal uncertainty reduction) and offshore site assessment from an on-shore location.

Offshore Power curve: to measure the wind for power curve verification, from the transition piece of an offshore turbine.

Wake measurement: to capture real-time wake effects turbine-to-turbine, farm-to-farm. If combined with a Wind Iris turbine-mounted Lidar data, it provides a comprehensive characterization of wake effects, at short and long distances, simultaneously.

Forecasting: to improve short-term and ramp event forecasting due to the capability of measuring wind several kilometers ahead of the wind farm.

WINDCUBE 100S/200S/400S: 3D wind mappers

The scanning WINDCUBE family uses the same pulsed Doppler technology as the well-known and widely used WINDCUBE vertical profiler.

Fiber technology used in all WINDCUBE Lidars is designed to meet strong operational requirements and optimal instrument compactness. The modularity allows use of the WINDCUBE 100S/200S/400S with different scanning scenarios (PPI, RHI, LOS, DBS) adapted to multiple applications.

WINDCUBE 100S/200S/400S offer the most advanced technique to measure the wind components on a large scale for short term campaigns or long term operations to reduce uncertainties, understand physical phenomena (such as wakes) or improve forecasting.

SCANNING SCENARIOS AND PERFORMANCE*

Scenario modes available	PHI (Plan Position Indicator) RHI (Range Height Indicator) DBS (Doppler Beam Swinging - Vertical profile) LOS (Sequential fixed Line of Sight measurements)
Wind measurement range	WINDCUBE 100S: 3.5 km (range resolution 50m, accumulation time 1 sec) WINDCUBE 200S: 6 km (range resolution 50m, accumulation time 1 sec) WINDCUBE 400S: 10 km (range resolution 150m, accumulation time 1 sec)
Maximum Lidar acquisition range	WINDCUBE 100S/200S: 12 km WINDCUBE 400S: 14 km
Wind speed range	Radial wind speed (PPI, RHI, LOS) : -30m/s to 30m/s

MEASUREMENT PARAMETERS

Accumulation time	0.5 to 10s (1 s is standard)
Physical range resolution	WINDCUBE 100S/200S: 25,50,75,100m WINDCUBE 400S: 75,100,150,200m
Scanner rotation speed	Up to 30°/s
Azimuth angle	Between 0° and 360° (with 0,1° increment)

*Note: The maximum range of velocity measurement depends on various parameters such as the accumulation time, physical range resolution, rotation speed and atmospheric conditions (visibility, type of aerosols and air turbulence).

HARDWARE AND ENVIRONMENTAL

Dimensions	(L-W-H) (mm): 1008 x 814 x 1365 (with scanning head and minimum feet extension)
Weight	232 kg (without options)
Outdoor conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Operating ambient temperature range: -25°C to+ 45°C (-13°....113 F°) IP65 (dust and splash water resistant) Operating humidity: 10% to 100% Resistant to salty environment (ISO 9227)
Laser source	Pulsed laser @ 1,54 um
Power consumption	500 W to 1.600 W (range includes use of coolers and heaters)

- Wind measurement to 10 km
- Full 3D fast scan
- Unattended and continuous operations
- Flexible configurations
- Ideal for short term campaigns (rental options available)

For further information about

WINDCUBE⁺
100S/200S/400S

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LEOSPHERE is a world leader in Lidar (laser radar) atmospheric remote observations. The company develops, sells and services new turnkey remote-sensing instruments allowing wind measurement and aerosol (ice, ash, dust, smoke) characterization.

LEOSPHERE has deployed hundreds of Lidars throughout the world in severe environments with the same concern of reliability, reduction of operational costs for clients, and dedication to atmospheric hazards control.

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